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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: www.nautilus-h2020.eu.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the global exploitation strategy of the NAUTILOS project, developed in the scope of WP11, with a focus on the 11 Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and presents the final Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap.

It builds upon previous WP11 deliverables related to exploitation, open-access instrumentation, brokerage protocols, and socio-economic impact assessments:

1. D11.1 - NAUTILOS Exploitation Strategy
2. D11.2 - Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap
3. D11.3 - Brokerage Events Meetings Protocols
4. D11.8 - NAUTILOS Socio-Economic Impact Assessment
5. D11.5 - NAUTILOS Socio-Economic Impact Assessment – final

The initial part of this report begins with the overview of the project results and NAUTILOS key exploitable results (KERs). It then presents the overall exploitation methodology, with an emphasis on commercial results. It outlines all activities carried out with partners under WP11, including: ownership and IPR analysis, cost structures, competitor and cost-benefit analysis, commercialisation strategies, stakeholder engagement and business plan development (including customer segments definition).

Each KER business plan is presented in its own dedicated section, following a consistent structure and the order outlined below:

1. MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag (CEiiA)
2. Silicate electrochemical sensor (NKE & CNRS)
3. Fluorescence data logger – WISENS TD-CHL- α (NKE)
4. Dissolved oxygen data logger – WISENS TD-DO (NKE)
5. Fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor (HES-SO)
6. Click & sound recorder (AQUATEC)
7. Active acoustic profiling data logger – Aquascap MK2 (AQUATEC)
8. Submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics (SubCTech)
9. Deep ocean CTD instrument / CT Sensor (UL-FE)
10. Deep ocean radioactivity data logger (HCMR)
11. SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag (CNRS/SMRU)

While detailed and comprehensive, these chapters provide a clear summary of the work undertaken to support the development of strong business plans that aim to ensure the long-term impact of each KER beyond the NAUTILOS project. As a public deliverable, this document also serves to inform interested stakeholders and share more about NAUTILOS key exploitable results.

The second part, addressing “Task 11.2 Instrumentation Roadmap: Scalability, Replicability, and Transferability Study,” outlines the efforts made to ensure the scalability of NAUTILOS KERs in alignment with specific global initiatives that support the project’s commercialization goals. Finally, a section is dedicated to present the final OIAR: the final database and the first Microsoft Power BI prototype, including major conclusions and opportunities for the future of this strategic tool.

The present deliverable concludes with a summarised overview of the work carried out by the WP11 team and NAUTILOS partners, highlighting their joint efforts to secure long-term impact—specifically through the democratisation of marine environmental monitoring.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AdriFOOS	Adriatic Fisheries and Oceanography Observing System
API	Application Programming Interface
AtlantOS	Optimising and Enhancing the Integrated Atlantic Ocean Observing Systems
BA	Business Analytics
BI	Business Intelligence
BMC	Business Model Canvas
Chl-<i>a</i>	Chlorophyll <i>a</i>
CNR-IRBIM	Institute for Biological Resources and Marine Biotechnology of the National Research Council
CNRS-LGC	Laboratoire de Génie Chimique - Centre national de la recherche scientifique
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth
D	Deliverable
DAX	Data Analysis Expressions
DFKI	German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
DTU AQUA	Danish National Institute of Aquatic Resources
EIC	European Innovation Council
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EU	European Union
FVON	Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network
GA	Grant Agreement
GPS	Global Positioning System
HCMR	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research

HEI	Higher Education Institute
IPR	Intellectual property rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NIVA	Norwegian Institute for Water Research
NKE	nke instrumentation
OIAR	Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PR	Project Result
SMRU	Sea Mammal Research Unit
TIB	Technology and Innovation Board
TIM	Technology and Innovation Manager
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UA	University of Aveiro
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders

I. INTRODUCTION

The exploitation of innovation results is a critical component in maximising the value of European research and innovation initiatives. Within the context of EU-funded projects, such as those under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe as NAUTILOS project, the effective exploitation of results plays a central role in achieving long-term impact and sustainability.

All NAUTILOS activities (technical, societal and policy oriented) are connected to one key objective from NAUTILOS project: to develop cost-effective instrumentation targeting a broad range of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

By the end of the NAUTILOS project, 11 commercial products are being made available, each demonstrating confirmed and significant advantages for ocean monitoring when compared to existing global market alternatives. This report details how continuous and cross-cutting activities under WP11 have supported the development of each technology along both the go-to-product and go-to-market pathways. Results to be presented in D11.7 reflect a strong commitment from the NAUTILOS consortium in developing innovative instrumentation to be delivered commercially with sustainable business strategies that further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

Considering that the challenges associated with ocean monitoring lie not only in the availability of instrumentation for effective data collection, as mentioned above, but also in the sharing of these monitoring solutions among various stakeholders, the NAUTILOS project tackles another market gap - the lack of an accessible database that centralises information on existing instruments and their technical specifications. D11.7 also presents the final database and the first Microsoft Power BI prototype of the Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap.

II. NAUTILOS RESULTS AND NAUTILOS EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

NAUTILOS RESULTS AND KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS (KER)

Project results are the measurable outcomes — tangible or intangible — achieved upon project completion. These results are crucial for assessing success, demonstrating impact, and guiding future initiatives. They also offer accountability, learning, and continuous improvement opportunities, showing how resources were used to meet goals.

The NAUTILOS project has provided over the last years of work a **significant variety of results from commercial products to citizen science tools, policy briefs and data and modelling products**. Results are reported along several deliverables connected to different NAUTILOS WP as described below:

- **Instrumentation results** are reported across various deliverables, with a primary focus on those from WP7, where the NAUTILOS field demonstrations are described. NAUTILOS instrumentation is presented on the website of the project: <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/sensors-samplers/>;
- **Data and modelling products results** are reported on “WP9 - Data Modelling and Data Sharing” deliverables. This WP aimed to demonstrate and quantify how the new sensors, the new integration in platforms and the new observation approaches developed in the project will improve the modelling capabilities. Results (<https://nautilus-h2020.eu/model-portal/>) show a significant improvement in forecasting capabilities when using NAUTILOS-like observations. An additional objective of this WP was to create a Data Sharing environment with main European data repositories such as EMODnet, which can be assessed in: <https://data-nautilus-h2020.eu/erddap/index.html> and <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/data-portal/>;
- **Policy briefs results**, reported on “WP10 - Outreach, Communication and Dissemination”. WP10 aims to maximise project visibility, foster continuous dialogue with stakeholders (including policymakers), raise public awareness, and promote NAUTILOS tools and outcomes. All briefs are publicly available on the NAUTILOS website (<https://nautilus-h2020.eu/policy-engagement/>) with descriptions in D10.3 and D10.10. Together, they provide actionable recommendations for sustainable and inclusive ocean observation across Europe;
- **Citizen science tools results** reported in WP10 (Task 10.4 - D10.9) and in “WP12 - Synergies with ESPCE” (D12.2 and D12.3), which also include some NAUTILOS instrumentation results. Plastic - related WP12 activities targeted a wide audience in the scope of NAUTILOS with over 50 citizen science campaigns in Greece, Italy, Norway and India, as well as two capacity building initiatives in Greece and Norway which have later achieved a wider-scale impact through the distribution of training courses as open access e-learning modules. In total, nearly one hundred citizen science activities were carried out. The Citizen Science tools of NAUTILOS are presented on the website of the project: <https://nautilus-h2020.eu/nautilus-cs-app/>.

All results are available on NAUTILOS website, on the results tab (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Access to NAUTILOS results on NAUTILOS webpage - Results tab.

Despite the wide variety of results from the NAUTILOS project, the “WP11- Exploitation and Impact” activities, and consequently NAUTILOS Exploitation strategy, focus primarily on **commercial results**. Commercial results can include products, services or citizen science tools, among others. However, in NAUTILOS, in alignment with the project goals “(...) to fill in marine observation and modelling gaps for biogeochemical, biological and deep ocean physics essential ocean variables and micro-/nano-plastics, by developing a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers (...)” **commercial results are naturally related with the instrumentation developed**. In fact, after interaction with all results owners, it was possible to conclude that **NAUTILOS commercial results included only instrumentation results**.

For all results not aiming for commercialisation (with other use models) other means of exploitation were discussed with teams. Specific alternative (non-commercial) exploitation options were shared with the consortium as: scientific publications and conferences, capacity building and training, policy recommendations. These actions lay the foundation for long-term impact and potential replication beyond NAUTILOS, ensuring that its outcomes continue to be used and adapted well beyond the project's lifetime.

Despite the focus on instrumentation on WP11, it is important to highlight that not all NAUTILOS instruments developed are considered for commercialisation. NAUTILOS generated **18 different instrument results, 16 of them original developments** (Table 1). Other results (carbonate sensors and phytoplankton sampler) are categorized as “COTS + additional developments” and thus not considered. For these ones, the exploitation suggestions included contacting the original manufacturer to share their additional developments and evaluate the possibility for licensing.

Facing the fact of having 16 original developments, and the considered effort to perform an exploitation analysis with each one of them, it was necessary to undergo a screening to evaluate NAUTILOS key exploitation results to prioritize results.

Table 1: NAUTILOS instrumentation results - original developments.

NAUTILOS instrumentation results - original developments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor ● Dissolved oxygen data logger WiSens TD-DO ● Fluorescence data logger WiSens TD – Chl-<i>a</i> ● Silicate electrochemical sensor ● Passive broadband acoustic recording sensor for noise monitoring ● Passive acoustic event recorder (porpoise & dolphin clicks for abundance estimation) ● Active acoustic profiling data logger AQUAscat Mk2 ● Submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics ● Deep ocean CTD instrument / CT sensor ● Deep ocean radioactivity sensor ● MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag ● SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag ● Microplastic sampler ● Microplastic detector ● Microplastic detector system (sampler + detector + FerryBox infrastructure) ● LIDAR
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A **key exploitable result (KER)** is an **identified main interesting result**, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education. **To select and prioritize results, it is recommended to use different criteria:** degree of innovation, exploitability and impact. As such, in the scope of WP11 and in agreement with the consortium, it was decided to consider the following criteria:

- must be an **original development** from NAUTILOS and aimed for commercialisation;
- must have **proven technical performance** (reported on WP7 demonstrations - TRL 6 or above);
- to be **ready for commercialisation (TRL9) up to 2029**;
- must have a **defined commercialisation strategy** until 31st of March of 2025, in particular for non-private partners who should either clearly express their intent to undertake commercialisation directly or present a concrete plan for engaging with another partner for commercialisation;
- must **collaborate with WP11 in conducting a market competitor analysis** (D11.5);
- must be available to **provide a cost structure assessment** (to produce the cost-benefit analysis; D11.5) until 31st of March of 2025;
- must **develop a business model canvas**, with WP11 support.

Considering all above criteria, it was possible to conclude to have 12 Key Exploitation Results from NAUTILOS project as described on Table 2.

Table 2: List of NAUTILOS exploitable results and partners involved (with references for IPR ownership).

NAUTILOS KER	Partner(s) involved
Fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor	HES-SO (IPR owner)
	NKE (housing provider; independent from sensor development)
Dissolved oxygen datalogger WiSens TD-DO	NKE
Fluorescence datalogger WiSens TD – Chl- <i>a</i>	NKE
Click and sound recorder ~~ 2 project results in one commercial product) ~~	AQUATEC
Active acoustic profiling data logger AQUAscat Mk2	AQUATEC
MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tags	CEiiA (IPR owner)
	IMAR (demo partner with no associated IPR)
SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag	CNRS-CEBC (demo partner with no associated IPR)
	SMRU (IPR owner - external partner)
Silicate electrochemical sensor	NKE (IPR co-owner)
	CNRS-LGC (IPR co-owner)
Submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics	SubCTech
Deep ocean CTD instrument / CT sensor	UL-FE
Deep ocean radioactivity sensor	HCMR

Table 2 presents the final NAUTILOS KERs designations. Appendix 2 provides a reference mapping between these designations and the original result names used in the NAUTILOS Grant Agreement.

A **comprehensive characterisation of the individual beneficiaries** of the project was performed and presented in D11.5. In the scope for the present report, it is important to **focus only on those partners taking the lead on NAUTILOS KERs**. NAUTILOS KERs are developed with contributions from 9 entities, which are based in different countries, namely France (CNRS and NKE), Germany (SubCTech), Greece (HCMR), Slovenia (UL-FE), Switzerland (HES-SO), Portugal (CEiiA, IMAR) and United Kingdom (AQUATEC). Concerning the type of organisations, four entities (45%) are public (two research bodies and two research body and higher education institutions), and five entities (55%) are private (two non-profit research

bodies, and three small and medium size enterprises). This is important to be reported in the present deliverable since **the type of entities in the consortium may influence the reality behind the exploitation strategy of the project**. For instance, companies such as SubCTech will directly commercialize their instrumentation, while instruments developed by non-private entities, such as HCMR, will require the involvement of an external commercial partner to bring them to market.

NAUTILOS EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

The exploitation strategy of NAUTILOS - “NAUTILOS Road to Market” - focuses on maximising the impact of all 11 commercial products (12 project results whereas one product combines two project results) generated from NAUTILOS, while at the same time fulfilling all expected activities in accordance to NAUTILOS Grant Agreement.

This report details how continuous and cross-cutting activities under WP11 have supported the development of each technology along both the go-to-product and go-to-market pathways. Several activities were developed in the scope of Tasks 11.1, T11.2 and T11.4 throughout NAUTILOS timeline, and partially made available on previous deliverables.

“NAUTILOS Road to Market” included distinguished **interaction activities**, led by the Technical and Innovation Manager (TIM; Catarina Rasquilha Lemos, CEiiA):

1. **Technology and Innovation Board meetings:** meetings organized by the TIM first to evaluate technical performance (go-to-product) as it is her role to lead the Technology and Innovation Board meetings, in alignment with PC, PM and WPLs. In 2022 a new concept of TIB meetings, more technically oriented, was defined to focus on the innovation uncertainties within NAUTILOS. TIB meetings were one of the most time-consuming activities from WP11 (yet with reduced expression on deliverables), and they proved to be critical to solve inter-WP challenges. Initially focused on instrumentation partners, soon they started involving platform owners and mission owners. As technical performance improved and the TRL increased, partners from WP11 (exploitation and impact) and WP9 (data sharing) began participating in the meetings. As such, TIB meetings covered all NAUTILOS Innovation Value Chain: Idea Generation - Development - Business Model/Product Launch. They took place every 3 months, until December 2024, and in general all invited partners took part and actively participated in those meetings despite their long duration, clearly stating the commitment of NAUTILOS consortium. When necessary, sensor-platform meetings were also suggested;
2. **One-to-one meetings:** if collective meetings as TIBs were relevant for the technical status, when it comes to discuss commercialisation, the best is to perform it individually. All business frameworks are different and some details must remain confidential. Interactions were organized monthly, except when not necessary. Meetings always included NAUTILOS TIM as also some other WP11 partners;
3. **In-person visits:** TIM’s favourite activity for challenging issues, as it allows for a close interaction and understanding of partner reality. For example, this type of interaction was critical to: define HCMR commercial strategy for the deep ocean radioactivity; to

define a solid alignment for the technical multi-platform mission held in Matosinhos – Portugal (Figure 2), as also to support CNRS-CEBC showcasing NAUTILOS results, mainly SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag at the SEA TECH WEEK 2024 (Figure 2). **A key activity to be considered for the future role of TIM in European projects.**

Figure 2: NAUTILOS “Road to Market” interaction activities: technology and innovation board meetings, one-to-one meetings and in-person visits.

Apart from the interaction activities, previously described, that pushed for active communication and clarification, “NAUTILOS Road to market” also included several **practical activities** (mandatory for all NAUTILOS KERs, however open to all NAUTILOS results):

- Go-to-product: status tables to assess technical performance;
- Go-to-market: individual merchandising materials development, brokerage events and other brokerage opportunities participation, individual business model canvas design, assessment of IPRs & Access Rights, definition of commercialisation strategies, cost structure and market competitors analysis, potential clients interactions and early sales evaluation.

All activities are briefly mentioned below, with references to previous deliverables if applicable.

“NAUTILOS Road to market” starts with assessing **technical performance**. With the benefit of NAUTILOS project structure, products were tested in several environments from lab to deep ocean, which led to high TRL products. To evaluate technical performance, technical status is essential. This was achieved through meetings and communication between partners; however, **status tables** were critical (Figure 3). They were developed using online shared documents on NAUTILOS Google drive folder, accessible to everyone. They were used during TIB meetings or any other requested opportunity as Consortium Meetings (a live session started to be implemented as a good practice). With this simple tool, it was possible to keep track of activities (color-coded for easier status). **Status tables started with a technical status** (common “database” for monitoring multi-WP objectives and challenges from development to integration and afterwards demonstration) **to status tables related to commercialisation and data sharing**. All invited partners took part in this status tables update (commonly updated by TIM or WPL).

Silicate Electrochemical Sensor -

The Silicate Electrochemical Sensor is developed by NKE Instrumentation and LEGOS-CNRS and will be incorporated onto a profiling float to measure silicate concentration up to 1000 m depth. The design of the electrochemical cell was adapted to decrease measurement frequency down to ~10 min. The silicomolybdc complex is formed in situ after the oxidation of a molybdenum electrode to form all the reagents needed. This complex is then detected on a gold working electrode, where the measured signal is directly proportional to silicate concentration in sea water. A calibration using silicate standards is needed before deployment to calibrate the sensor.

[DOWNLOAD LEAFLET](#)

Measured parameters

Silicate concentration and seawater temperature

Expected final TRL

TRL 8

Demonstration Location

Mediterranean Sea

Point of Contact

Arnaud David

adavid@nke.fr

Carole Barus

carole.barus@univ-tlse3.fr

Figure 6: NAUTILOS commercial leaflets developed for all NAUTILOS Key exploitation results available for download on NAUTILOS Website - Results tab - Sensors/samplers tab (<https://nautilus-h2020.eu/resources/#Sensors-Samplers-Leaflets>).

For some products, additional **dedicated merchandising materials** were developed. These include company-branded promotional content, detailed data sheets, technical manuals, instructional videos, and even usability sessions. Further details are provided in the individual KER sections below.

As soon as the NAUTILOS instrumentation demonstrated proven technical performance, market engagement began to intensify, primarily through NAUTILOS brokerage events and other opportunities (D11.3). NAUTILOS initiated this process with its first brokerage event during the Ocean Race Summit in Genoa (Italy, June 2023), marking the start of a broader exploitation strategy and direct interaction with potential clients. Further **brokerage activities** took place across key events in Spain, Denmark, Belgium, UK and USA. An additional participation occurred in France during Sea Tech Week 2024 (Figure 7). Full details on all brokerage events and related opportunities are available in D11.3.

At these events, NAUTILOS maintained dedicated booths showcasing results, offering commercial leaflets, and distributing other communication materials developed by WP10. **Over 200 meaningful interactions expressing interest in NAUTILOS instrumentation** were

recorded, with contacts shared among partners and used to promote the NAUTILOS final event. These engagements, along with early sales opportunities, were further explored during WP11 activities, including one-to-one meetings and in-person visits.

Figure 7: NAUTILOS SEA TECH WEEK 2024 booth, with 3 partners (CEiiA, CNRS-CEBC and NKE) attending and showcasing 3 commercial products developed in the scope of NAUTILOS (left). Merchandising material developed for all NAUTILOS project and NAUTILOS KERs at European Maritime Day 2024 booth (right).

By the end of 2024, NAUTILOS' formal presence at public events had concluded. However, it was evident that **partners such as SubCTech, NKE, and AQUATEC continued to showcase NAUTILOS products within their commercial portfolios** - both in printed materials and at live exhibitions, as seen at Ocean Business 2025 (Figure 8). Additionally, throughout the project, several partners attended targeted events that were strategically important for their individual business development, such as the case of UL-FE partner.

Figure 8: NAUTILOS sensors and samplers at Ocean Business 2025 - the final ocean-oriented exhibition before NAUTILOS closure: SubCTech booth showcasing the official SubCTech leaflet with NAUTILOS sensor displayed (left); NKE booth showcasing WiSens TD - Chl-a and WiSens TD - DO sensors (right).

Practical activities, developed in the scope of T11.1, T11.2 and T11.4 tasks, included also:

- Definition of target blue economy sectors and target customer segments for each KER;
- Definition or development of a clear commercialisation strategy. While this is easier with private companies, other partners struggled to find a go-to-market strategy. In the scope of WP11 several one-to-one-meetings as also in-person visits focused on this and ultimately led to find a commercial partner for all products (including partners external to NAUTILOS consortium);
- Analysis and assessment of IPRs (foreground, sideground, postground in sequence of background analysis - stated on NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement) & Access Rights, to avoid conflicts within the Consortium and foster the deployment of the results at European and international scale (co-ownership contributions per partner were discussed and agreed by e-mail);
- Cost structure consolidation and market competitors analysis in order to produce a cost-benefit analysis (D11.5; Figure 9);
- Future use of NAUTILOS units.

Figure 9: NAUTILOS cost-benefit analysis classification

All activities together, consolidated go-to-product and go-to-market paths and made it possible to define each KER business plan. For that a strategic management template called “Business Model Canvas” (BMC) was used. It is made up of nine building blocks, showing the logic of how a company intends to deliver value and make money, supporting a simple and visual communication of a business model. To introduce partners into the BMC tool a practical session was organized in CEiiA headquarters by +ATLANTIC CoLAB, in November 2023, whereas BMC for MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag was shared as an example (Figure 10).

BMC for all KER were developed during individual meetings with partners and are presented below on the following individual sections. All BMC follow some assumptions:

- This BMC represents the most realistic scenario for the future commercialisation of each product;
- It considers WP11 activities already as part of this go-to-market strategy;
- When an external partner is considered for the commercialisation of any NAUTILOS KER, those partners were involved in BMC development. All co-ownership and commercial agreements were discussed and will be formally concluded when the

product reaches a commercial TRL, as joint development will continue for the future beyond NAUTILOS;

- In the Cost Structure section of the Business Model Canvas, fixed costs are differentiated from variable costs. The main difference between the two types of costs is that variable costs depend on the sales volume (e.g., acquisitions of raw materials, parts, payloads, and extra technical support that depends on customer needs), while fixed costs are mainly constant regardless of how many units are sold (e.g. infrastructures maintenance, human resources, basic technical support).

Figure 10: Business model Canvas template (source: Strategyzer; left). Business model canvas template practical session (Matosinhos, Portugal, November 2023; right).

III. MAANTA NAUTILOS ANIMAL TAG (CEiIA)

MAANTA is a product line from CEiIA. It stands out for non-invasive towed or mounted marine animal tagging platforms for measuring behavioural and oceanic data, reducing data gaps, increasing animal awareness, and tailoring conservation efforts. MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag (Figure 11) - a **non-invasive towed tagging system** used for animals such as manta rays and sharks was developed in the scope of the NAUTILOS project featuring a **dissolved oxygen sensor**, to allow for the monitoring of dissolved oxygen and correlation with other oceanographic parameters, as **no other non-invasive tagging solution available worldwide** (D11.5). Its highly hydrodynamic design ensures **minimal drag**, and its customisable data acquisition (e.g., depth-triggered logging) meets diverse research needs. The platform has demonstrated **high reliability** with a **100% recovery rate to date**, reinforcing its usability for **multi-mission deployments** (durable, compact and reusable tags). It fills a significant data gap in ocean monitoring, supporting both conservation initiatives and scientific research, **highly contributing to researchers' success**.

maanta

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All configurations are eligible for customized development
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CEiIA.COM

CATARINA.LEMOS@CEiIA.COM

A non-invasive towed marine animal (sharks and mantas) tagging platform for measuring behavioral and oceanic data.

Measurable parameters	dissolved oxygen NEW depth temperature acceleration orientation velocity
Dissolved oxygen range	0 to 23 mg/L (± 0.01)
Temperature range	-20 to 60 °C (± 2)
Tracking	satellite & radio
Temperature range	-20 to 60 °C
Depth rating	2 000 m
Mission duration	up to 1 week
Battery	easy-swap & rechargeable
Data	fast download & easy-swap memory card
Mission planning	CEiIA user interface (Maanta app)
Dimensions (L x W x H)	375 x 120 x 155 mm
Weight (air)	1.1 kg
Weight (water)	+180 g (positive buoyancy)

Figure 11: MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag (CEiIA) leaflet.

As reported in D7.6, MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag was deployed in all targeted species successfully (Figure 11). Notably, **100% of the deployed tags were successfully recovered, accounting for above 1000 hours of data collection**. All major challenges encountered during the project were successfully addressed, demonstrating strong problem-solving capabilities and commitment to overcoming unforeseen obstacles from both partners involved (CEiiA and IMAR). These achievements have contributed to enhancing the overall robustness of the MAANTA NAUTILOS system, which concludes its participation in the NAUTILOS project with a **clear focus on commercialisation**. The successful deployments carried out during missions across the **Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Oceans** also reflect the project's strong commitment to the global expansion and applicability of MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag. The first sale is expected to happen for a Pacific Ocean marine reserve.

Figure 12: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag, in an operational environment (more information in D7.6): whale shark tagging in Azores (Atlantic Ocean) by IMAR Team (right); datasets made available through the NAUTILOS data portal on the project website (right).

As part of WP11, a thorough competitor and market analysis was conducted, resulting in a cost-benefit analysis classification for the tagging system MAANTA NAUTILOS (see Deliverable 11.5 - Final Socio-Economic Impact Assessment). The tag was classified as **“New to Market”**, meaning that there is no equivalent or comparable competitor on the market.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific technology under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented in Figure 15 and serves as the starting point for the work to be further discussed during the BOOSTER initiative.

Customer Segments

MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag targets a **diverse yet focused customer base**. Some of the specific examples below (marked with *) result from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Academic researchers in marine ecology and oceanography** (e.g., IMAR, BIMS Institute*, Universidad San Francisco de Quito*);

- **Media and storytelling platforms**, including documentary and storytelling organisations and visual media producers focusing on marine wildlife and ocean conservation;
- **Other customers**, such as local, national and supranational authorities for ocean monitoring (e.g., IPCC), marine conservation foundations (e.g., Charles Darwin Foundation*, Jocotoco*, Manta Trust*, Save Our Seas Foundation), and National Parks (e.g., Galapagos National Park*).

Channels

MAANTA's outreach spans both offline and online efforts. Online presence will be maintained via **websites (NAUTILOS and CEiiA)**, **NAUTILOS newsletter**, **scientific publications**, and targeted **social media** and **email campaigns**. Additionally, **documentaries** serve as powerful storytelling tools that amplify brand visibility. Offline strategies include **direct technical visits**, **participation in specialised fairs** (e.g., NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities - Oceanology, UN Ocean Conference 2024 (Figure 13), Sea Tech Week 2024) and **conferences** (e.g., Jornada Nacional de Elasmobrânquios, International Conference on Fish Telemetry), and branding through physical materials including: **NAUTILOS leaflet and product materials** developed by CEiiA.

Figure 13: MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag (CEiiA) showcased at United Nations Ocean Conference 2024, one of several NAUTILOS brokerage opportunities organized in the scope of WP11: WP10 and WP11 representatives at the “ALL Atlantic” booth, with NAUTILOS merchandising (left); MAANTA NAUTILOS being presented by Catarina Lemos (CEiiA) to the Galapagos Marine Conservation Team, after discussing a possible future collaboration beyond NAUTILOS (right).

Apart from the NAUTILOS leaflet, developed specifically under WP11 to include key features of the sensor and to help to communicate the sensor's value proposition to a broad audience, CEiiA team took a step forward, with NAUTILOS support and in the scope of WP11, **to improve their product from the marketing point of view and to ensure a greater user experience** by developing or renewing the following materials (Figure 14):

- High-resolution digital computation **3D files**;
- Instructional **video for assembly**;
- Product **data sheet** and redesign of all **technical manuals and product casing**.

As part of the process, internal tests were organised with non-experienced users and products developed were tested in the scope of a **detailed usability testing plan, during 2023**. Also, all materials were shared with NAUTILOS partners, as a reference of what could be further developed for other instrumentation.

Figure 14: MAANTA NAUTILOS materials developed by CEiiA in the scope of WP11.

Customer Relationships

CEiiA builds **strong, trust-based relationships** through personalised service and technical reliability. This includes **pre- and post-mission support, surveys, and progress calls** to tailor the experience to individual researchers and organisations.

Revenue Streams

CEiiA operates under a **fixed pricing model** when it comes to MAANTA NAUTILOS, with **direct product sales** at the core. Revenue is supplemented through optional services such as **extra technical support, data analysis and post-processing and tag customisation**. A **variable billing system** accommodates pre- and post-payment options, ensuring adaptability to client needs.

Key Resources

Essential resources for the development of MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag are **production facilities, materials (payload and bus) and quality testing laboratories**. Additionally, **engineering teams for mechanical and electronic development** as well as its multidisciplinary teams: mechanical and electronics engineers, data scientists, and legal/IP experts. Its **manufacturing facilities** and quality assurance infrastructure enable high-standard

production. The organisation also benefits from experienced **sales** and dissemination professionals, ensuring effective delivery from design to deployment.

Key Activities

To manufacture MAANTA NAUTILOS tags, there are key activities that are needed, including the **design and manufacturing of customisable tags**, the development of highly configurable **electronics** to increase tag adaptability, **mission planning** and **technical support provision** (e.g., software, hardware), **marketing and sales**, and **ongoing R&D** to remain competitive.

Key Partnerships

MAANTA NAUTILOS success is underpinned by **strategic collaborations** with **universities** and **research centers**, particularly those contributing to marine sciences and sensor technology. Key partnerships include suppliers of specialised components (e.g., **dissolved oxygen sensors**), raw materials and parts suppliers, as well as **partners to support field testing and demonstrations**, including offshore environments and pressure housing facilities. Additionally, documentary and storytelling organisations constitute essential partners.

<p>Key Partnership</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities and research centers Specialized sensor suppliers for tag (e.g., dissolved oxygen sensor) customization Documentary and storytelling organizations Partners to perform testing and demonstration (e.g., relevant offshore testing, pressure housing testing) Raw materials, parts suppliers 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design and manufacturing of customizable tags. Development of highly configurable electronics to increase tag adaptability Mission planning and technical support provision (e.g., software; hardware) Marketing & Sales Continuous R&D to stay competitive and improve the product <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engineering team for mechanical and electrical development Manufacturing facilities, materials (payload and bus) and quality testing laboratories Data science team to transform raw data into actionable insights for clients (when applicable) Sales and dissemination HR Expertise in IP management and contracts. 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A non-invasive towed marine animal (sharks and mantas) tagging platform for measuring behavioral and oceanic data, reducing data gaps, increasing animal awareness and tailoring conservation efforts Features a dissolved oxygen sensor, as no other non-invasive tagging solution available worldwide (based on NAUTILOS competitors' analysis) Highly hydrodynamic tags causing minimal drag to animals Configurable features, such as recording data only under specific conditions (e.g., below certain depths) Reliable, durable, compact and reusable tags; Optimised for multiple missions as those happening in the scope of NAUTILOS WP7 deployments in the Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Oceans; Easy deployment and recovery (100% recovery rate up to now) The main tool for the researcher's success (in terms of monitoring the dissolved oxygen and correlation with other oceanographic parameters) 	<p>Customer relationship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trusted brand with experience in past missions Direct contact through technical visits (pre-mission, mission support, post-mission follow-ups). Personalized support via surveys, progress calls, and continuous engagement to ensure client satisfaction. Expertise and reliability to instill confidence in clients. <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Branding: product, leaflet (NAUTILOS; CEiA), marketing content Technical visits at various phases of missions Presence at specialized fairs (e.g., Oceanology*, United Nations Conference 2024*) and conferences (e.g., Jornada Nacional de Elasmobranchios, International Conference on Fish Telemetry, Sea Tech Week 2024*) Word-of-mouth from previous customers Online <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website (NAUTILOS, CEiA) NAUTILOS newsletter Success stories and scientific papers to showcase achievements Promotion through documentaries referencing the brand Email marketing and active social media campaigns <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine ecology researchers (IMAR, Universidad San Francisco de Quito*, BIMS Institute*) Universities and academic programs conducting marine science research. Media and storytelling platforms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentary and storytelling organizations Visual media producers focusing on marine wildlife and ocean conservation. Others <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local, national and supranational authorities for ocean monitoring (e.g. IPCC) Marine conservation foundations (e.g., Charles Darwin Foundation*, Jocotoco*, Manta Trust, Save our Seas Foundation). National Parks (e.g., Galapagos National Park*). <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage events</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human resources (engineering, operational and sales teams) Manufacturing infrastructures Intellectual Property and Legal Marketing and branding Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and 2-year guarantee) Variable <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw material acquisition Production costs Customizations Technical support (extra support) Shipping and logistics Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) royalties (if applicable) 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>Fixed pricing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Product sales Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extra technical support Data analysis and post-processing Product customization Payment type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 15: Business Model Canvas for MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag, designed by Daniel Costa and Paulo Figueiredo (CEiA), and WP11 Team.

Cost Structure

The major costs involved in manufacturing the MAANTA NAUTILOS tag are divided between fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include expenses with **human resources (engineering, operational and sales teams)**, **manufacturing infrastructures**, **intellectual property and legal**, **marketing and branding**, and **basic technical support** (pre-established HR hours and 2-year guarantee). On the other hand, **variable costs** include **raw material acquisition**, **production costs**, **customisations**, **technical support** (extra service), **shipping and logistics**,

marketing expenses (in particular, the organisation of exhibitions), and **royalties** (if applicable).

In continuity with the preceding Business Model Canvas analysis, the following Table 3 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process. It encompasses strategic considerations related to both product and business development, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 3: MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag (CEiiA) Exploitation ID card.

MAANTA NAUTILOS ANIMAL TAG (CEiiA) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 2 developed units will remain available for IMAR deployments for future <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.6)</small>
	Not applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership 100% CEiiA
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by CEiiA (development partner); IMAR as a commercial partnership <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS and CEiiA); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis New to Market <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis No direct competitors <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

IV. SILICATE ELECTROCHEMICAL SENSOR (NKE & CNRS)

The **silicate electrochemical sensor** (Figure 16) offers an innovative approach with **reagent-free silicate measurement**, for depths of **up to 1000 meters**. It is relatively compact and easy to use, and unlike competing solutions, it eliminates the operational limits of traditional reagent-based systems by requiring no reagent bags. Once it requires no replacement reagents, it results in **lower maintenance costs, faster measurements** and no restrictions on its lifetime tied to chemical conservation when compared with competing solutions. These features make it the **most reliable, efficient, and user-friendly** option for **long-term silicate monitoring in deep-sea environments**.

Silicate electrochemical sensor

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000025 (NAUILOS)
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NAUILOS

Electrochemical sensor for silicate measurement down to 1000 meters.

Measurable parameters	silicate concentration based on electrochemical method temperature pressure
Silicate range	0 to 132.8 µmol/L (± 1.0)
Temperature range	-2 to 35 °C (± 0.02)
Depth rating	1000 m
Dimensions	250 x Ø90 mm
Weight (air)	2.2 kg
Power consumption	provided by external platform (12 VDC)
Communication protocol with float	EMAP
Communication protocol with sensor	RS-232 serial port
Protocol for communication with PC	HTML, FTP and TELNET

Figure 16: Silicate electrochemical sensor (NKE & CNRS) leaflet.

As reported in D7.5, the silicate electrochemical sensor was **deployed successfully in the Mediterranean Sea**, using **NKE Argo Float platforms** (Figure 17). WP7 activities aimed to show correct sensor function at sea, while **measuring silicate concentrations, during almost 48 hours and up to over 500 m**. Future development plans, jointly with CNRS-LGC, include to advance this instrument to a commercial TRL. As reported in D7.5, **sensor performed in line with the established plan**, and it went smoothly with no issues to be highlighted.

Figure 17: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the silicate electrochemical sensor, in an operational environment (more information in D7.5): on the Mediterranean Sea, with the silicate electrochemical sensor developed by NKE (left); datasets made available through the NAUTILOS data portal on the project website (right).

As part of WP11, a thorough competitor and market analysis was conducted, resulting in a cost-benefit analysis classification for the silicate electrochemical sensor (D11.5). The sensor was classified as **“Improved Technology and Cheaper in Class”**, meaning that it is not only the cheapest sensor on the market, but also that the benefits and technical features of the NAUTILOS sensors are considered best fit for ocean monitoring.

Considering **that silicate concentration is one of the Essential Ocean Variables for which only a few instrumentation for ocean monitoring is available** it is essential to highlight the importance of NAUTILOS and European funding to develop a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, namely by developing innovative and breakthrough instrumentation for ocean monitoring cheaper and better for the environment.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific sensor under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented on Figure 18.

Customer segments

The electrochemical silicate sensor is tailored for a diverse range of customers involved in **marine and freshwater monitoring, regulation, and research**. Some of the specific examples below (marked with *) result from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Marine research institutions** deploying long-term monitoring systems such as **moorings, ARGO floats, and cabled observatories** (e.g., PNO Innovation*);
- **Marine monitoring organisations** (e.g., INILAB*);
- **Regulatory agencies** responsible for coastal water quality and compliance with the **Water Framework Directive (WFD)**;

- **Environmental protection agencies** monitoring nutrient dynamics and pollution impacts in both marine and freshwater environments;
- **Drinking and wastewater treatment facilities** where silicate levels are a key parameter;
- **Local governments and regulatory bodies** evaluating freshwater quality.

Channels

The strategy for reaching targeted customers considers both **digital and in-person channels** to effectively promote and deliver the electrochemical silicate sensor. The official **websites of NAUTILOS and NKE Instrumentation** serve as key information hubs, providing detailed technical specifications and product updates. **NAUTILOS sensor leaflet**, developed specifically under WP11, includes key features of the sensor and can help to communicate the sensor's value proposition to a broad audience. **Direct business-to-business contact** plays a crucial role in building strong, tailored relationships with customers. This is supported by a **worldwide network of experienced sales agents** who provide localised support and extend the market reach. Additionally, it is also important to ensure a strong presence at **specialised exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows**. In that sense, the sensor was showcased in several events such as the Sea Tech Week 2024 promoted in the scope of NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3), where direct interactions with potential customers and new collaboration opportunities were explored.

Customer relationships

Regarding how relationships are built and maintained with each customer segment, a **constant engagement with customers** throughout the entire process (**from sales to installation**) is prioritised. As part of this, **remote or on-site technical assistance** is provided whenever necessary or requested by the customer.

Revenue Streams

Main revenue comes from **direct product sales**, however **additional fees**, such as an **annual service**, which depend on customer needs, can be a revenue source. In terms of how the customer can pay for the products, a **variable billing system** (pre or post-payment) can be considered. Additionally, the silicate sensor has a **fixed pricing**.

Key Resources

Key resources include physical assets such as **raw materials, parts, payload, and production facilities** equipped to handle the assembly and integration of sensor payloads. Specialised human resources are equally essential, including **production and support engineers** who ensure high-quality manufacturing and customer service, and specialised engineers, particularly in **metrology** which is critical to sensor calibration and performance validation. The **sales team** plays a vital role in driving market engagement, managing client relationships, and expanding the customer base globally. To address sustainability and regulatory expectations, an **LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) specialist** to assess and minimise the environmental impact of the products throughout their lifecycle. Additionally, in-house professionals in **intellectual property (IP) management and contract law** ensure that innovations are protected and that all partnerships and agreements are strategically sound to avoid potential breaches in the latter.

Key Activities

Core activities span the entire lifecycle of the silicate electrochemical sensor, from development to post-sale technical support. The first critical activity is the **development and manufacturing of the sensors**, ensuring the sensor meets the highest standards of performance, reliability, and depth capability. **Sales operations** are central, involving both direct customer engagement and coordination with the global network of agents to reach diverse markets. **Quality assurance and metrology services** play a critical role in guaranteeing sensor accuracy and compliance with industry standards. Finally, **dedicated technical support** is essential to assist customers with deployment, maintenance, and optimal use of the sensor.

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong collaborative relationship with CNRS-LGC Payload suppliers (e.g. sensor) Electronics Components Suppliers Distributors 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development and manufacturing Sales Quality and Metrology services Technical support Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical (raw materials, parts, payload and production facilities) Workforce: Production and support engineers Specialised engineers (e.g. for metrology) Sales team Environmental impact: LCA expert Expertise in IP management and contracts 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrochemical sensor for silicate measurement down to 1000 meters* Relatively compact Easy-to-use with no reagent bags/change of reagent bags required like no other competitor No lifetime limitation due to non-conservation of reagents when compared to competitors Provides faster measurements while, at the same time, requiring less maintenance <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activities in the Mediterranean Sea.</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constantly engaging with customers Remote or on-site technical assistance Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website (NAUTILOS and NKE Instrumentation) NAUTILOS sensor leaflet NAUTILOS newsletter Personalised direct contacts (Business to business) Worldwide network of sales agents Specialized exhibitions, Conferences and Trade Shows (e.g. EMD 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage events & Opportunities</p>	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine research: can be deployed on moorings/ARGO floats, observatory cables (e.g. PNO Innovation*) Marine Monitoring (e.g. INILAB*) Marine regulatory agencies for coastal water quality and for compliance with the WFD Environmental Agencies Drinking and wastewater treatment plants Local government and regulatory authorities in relation to freshwater <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage events</p>
Cost Structure <p>Fixed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human resources (engineering, operational and sales teams) Manufacturing Infrastructures (e.g. metrology laboratory) Regulatory compliance, CE marking/Environmental Technology Verification Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and guarantee) <p>Variable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquisition of raw materials, parts and payload Expenses with calibration, testing and demonstration Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) Extra technical support (if requested by the customer, e.g. first try installation for long term operation) Royalties (if applicable) 		Revenue Streams <p>Fixed pricing</p> <p>Type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct sales of sensors Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual service <p>Payment type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 18: Business Model Canvas for the silicate electrochemical sensor, designed by Damien Malarde (nke instrumentation) and WP11 Team.

Key partnerships

The **strong collaborative relationship with CNRS-LGC** supports previous, ongoing and future development. During NAUTILOS development, this partner took the responsibility for electrochemical processes development, analytical chemistry expertise, sensor calibration and validation in natural waters and environmental conditions (support that is expected to continue for the future, up to TRL9). Other partners include a **few suppliers for electronic and payload components** which are particularly relevant for maintaining a reliable and efficient manufacturing process. In addition, **collaboration with distributors** is important for supporting the delivery of the products and services to customers.

Cost structure

The major costs involved in manufacturing the silicate electrochemical sensor are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include expenses with **human resources** (engineering, operational and sales teams), **manufacturing infrastructures** (e.g. **metrology laboratory**), **regulatory compliance**, **CE marking/Environmental Technology Verification** and **basic technical support** (pre-established HR hours and guarantee). On the other hand, **variable costs** include **raw materials, parts and payload acquisition**, expenses with **calibration, testing and demonstration**, **marketing expenses** (in particular, the organisation of

exhibitions), **extra technical support** (if requested by the customer, as for first try installation for long term operation), and **royalties** (if applicable in the future agreement).

As described on Table 4, the silicate electrochemical sensor has **shared IPR ownership** - the **only NAUTILOS KER in this situation**. Considering this sensitive situation several actions were performed in the scope of NAUTILOS:

- To avoid potential breaches in property rights, both entities agreed on each partner contribution, concerning the final sensor development status until the of NAUTILOS project (e-mail shared with both partners):
 - NKE | Full development of silicate electrochemical sensor with CNRS-LGC as partnership;
 - CNRS-LGC | Electrochemical processes development; analytical chemistry expertise sensor’s calibration and validation in natural waters and environmental conditions.
- An in-person visit took place between NAUTILOS TIM and Yves Degres (nke instrumentation), in October 2024, when it was possible to understand a past and positive background of other technology transfer processes between CNRS-LGC and NKE. It was agreed to continue to advance this instrument up to TRL9 before concluding the clear terms for knowledge transfer between both partners.

Table 4: Silicate electrochemical sensor (NKE & CNRS) Exploitation ID card.

SILICATE ELECTROCHEMICAL SENSOR (NKE & CNRS) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 1 developed prototype for further tests and development remains available for NKE <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.5)</small>
	Applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership NKE and CNRS-LGC
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by NKE (joint initiatives ongoing & licensing agreement under discussion with CNRS-LGC) <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology and Cheaper in Class <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor’s analysis One single competitor <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

V. FLUORESCENCE DATA LOGGER | WISENS TD-CHL- α (NKE)

The fluorescence data logger | WISENS TD-CHL- α (Figure 19) is an **autonomous, Wi-Fi-enabled underwater datalogger** designed for precise chlorophyll- α measurement at **depths of up to 600 meters**. It can operate independently in a **standalone mode** - logging data internally - or be **connected to a transmitter for real-time communication**. **Compact, robust, and highly durable**, it is designed to perform reliably in aggressive and extreme environments, with integration options for use on trawlers, nets, and traps. With internal battery powering operations, this device ensures **uninterrupted deployment and data acquisition** without external power requirements, enabling **long-term deployments**.

WiSens TD - Chl-a

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000625 (NAUTILOS)

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An autonomous Wi-Fi underwater datalogger for chlorophyll-a measurement down to 600 meters.

Measurable parameters	chlorophyll-a (based on the principle of fluorescence measured at 90°) temperature pressure
Chlorophyll-a range	0 to 500 ppb* (linearity: $r^2 > 0.99$)
Temperature range	-2 to 30 °C (± 0.02)
Depth rating	600 m
Dimensions	220 x Ø45 mm
Weight (air)	377 g
Power consumption	lithium batteries (3.6 VDC)
Data transfer	automatic via WiHub or manual via Android
Data communication protocol	Wi-Fi
Compatible	IOS, MAC OS, Windows and Android
*equivalent µg/L	

Figure 19: Fluorescence data logger | WiSens TD - Chl- α (NKE) leaflet.

As reported in D7.1 and D7.2, the WISENS TD - Chl- α was involved in **NAUTILOS demonstration activities in several locations** and with several collaborating partners, **from the Adriatic Sea to the Norwegian Sea**. This demonstration action - made possible through the NAUTILOS project and with support from the European Union - shows that, from a technical performance perspective, the prototype functioned well in a realistic environment,

however further development is still necessary (already planned internally at NKE) to advance the system to TRL 9, as commercialisation efforts are already underway (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted in an operational environment - the Adriatic Sea: (more information in D7.1 and D7.2): WiSens TD - DO and WiSens - Chl-a on a commercial fishing vessel (left); datasets recorded via AdriFOOS infrastructure and made available through the NAUTILOS data portal on the project website (right).

As part of WP11, a thorough competitor and market analysis was conducted, resulting in a cost-benefit analysis classification for the chlorophyll-*a* data logger (D11.5). The data logger was classified as **“Improved Technology”**, which means that its features are considered best fit for ocean monitoring compared with other comparable sensors available on the market.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific data logger under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented on Figure 22.

Customer segments

The fluorescence data logger can be applied in a diverse range of customer segments involved in **aquatic environmental monitoring and water quality management**. Some of the specific examples below (marked with *) result from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Marine research institutions** (e.g., PNO Innovation*);
- **Institutions specialised in Marine Monitoring** (e.g., Sternula*, INILAB*);
- **Marine Regulatory Agencies** responsible for monitoring coastal water quality and ensuring compliance with environmental directives, such as the **Water Framework Directive (WFD)**;
- **Environmental Agencies** that oversee ecosystem health and pollution control across aquatic environments;
- **Water Utilities and Treatment Facilities** that require real-time water quality monitoring to ensure safe water monitoring;
- **Local Governments and Regulatory authorities** evaluating freshwater quality;
- **Aquaculture and fisheries companies** (e.g., CNR, FVON) performing monitoring of water conditions to maintain healthy stock, optimize productivity, and meet sustainability standards.

Channels

The means through which the fluorescence data logger is promoted and delivered to its customer segments include both **digital and in-person channels**. The official **websites of the NAUTILOS project and nke instrumentation** serve as key information hubs, providing detailed technical specifications and product updates. **NAUTILOS leaflet and NKE's leaflet** (recently updated to include this data logger sensor in its commercial portfolio; Figure 21), summarises the key features of the data logger and can be an important channel to promote the value proposition. Direct **business-to-business** contact plays a crucial role in building strong, tailored relationships with customers. This is supported by a **worldwide network of experienced sales agents** who provide localised support and extend the market reach. Additionally, it is also important to ensure a **strong presence at specialised exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows**. In that sense, the sensor was **showcased in several events during the NAUTILOS project**, such as Sea Tech Week 2024, either on NAUTILOS or NKE booths (Figure 21), where direct interactions with potential customers were explored.

Figure 21: NKE NAUTILOS instrumentation showcased in both NAUTILOS and NKE booths at SEA TECH WEEK 2024, one of several NAUTILOS brokerage opportunities organized in the scope of WP11: NAUTILOS booth (left); NKE booth (right).

Customer relationships

Building and maintaining relationships with each customer segment is prioritised, with constant **engagement with customers** throughout the entire process (from sales to installation). As part of this, **remote or on-site technical assistance** is provided whenever necessary or requested by the customer, whether to support the operation or installation of the data logger or to solve technical issues. Overall, the relationships established with customers are **highly focused** on their needs and specifications.

Revenue Streams

The fluorescence data logger is available at a **fixed price**. There are various ways to possibly generate revenue from each customer segment, whether it is through **direct product sales or additional fees**, depending on customer needs. Additional fees include the possibility of contracting an **annual service** or to request for the **real-time transmission feature**. In terms of how the customer can pay for the products, a **variable billing system** can be considered.

Key Resources

The successful development and commercialisation of the fluorescence data logger depend on a combination of **physical, human, and intellectual resources**. Physical resources include **raw materials, specialised parts and payloads**, along with access to dedicated **production facilities** that ensure quality and efficiency. Human resources are equally important and include **production and support engineers** responsible for assembly, deployment, and maintenance, as well as **metrology engineers**, who are responsible for calibration and performance validation. A skilled **sales team** supports commercial partnerships.

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payload suppliers (e.g. sensor) • Distributors • Electronics Components Suppliers • Strong collaborative relationship with marine research institutes 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and manufacturing • Sales • Quality and Metrology services • Technical support Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical (raw materials, parts, payload and production facilities) • Workforce: Production and support engineers • Specialised engineers (e.g. for metrology) • Sales team 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An autonomous Wi-Fi underwater datalogger for chlorophyll-a measurement down to 600 meters* • Suitable to be deployed independently, either in a standalone configuration, only recording data, or connected to a transmitter • Robust, Small, compact • Suitable/Compliant for aggressive/extreme environment • Integrable on trawlers, nets and traps • Internal battery to provide power <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activities in the Mediterranean Sea and Atlantic Ocean</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constantly engaging with customers • Remote or on-site technical assistance • Highly customer focused Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website (NAUTILOS and NKE Instrumentation) • NAUTILOS datalogger leaflet, NKE leaflet • NAUTILOS newsletter • Personalised direct contacts (Business to business) • Worldwide network of sales agents • Specialized exhibitions, Conferences and Trade Shows (e.g. Ocean* Sciences Meeting 2024*, Oceanology International 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage events & Opportunities</p>	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine research (e.g. PNO Innovation Portugal*) • Marine Monitoring (e.g. Sternula*, INILAB*) • Marine regulatory agencies for coastal water quality and for compliance with the WFD • Environmental Agencies • Drinking and wastewater treatment plants • Local government and regulatory authorities in relation to freshwater • Aquaculture, fisheries (e.g. CNR, FVON) <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage events</p>
Cost Structure <p>Fixed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources (engineering, operational and sales teams) • Manufacturing infrastructures (e.g. metrology laboratory) • Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and guarantee) <p>Variable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition of raw materials, parts and payload • Expenses with calibration, testing and demonstration • Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) • Extra technical support (if requested by the customer, e.g. first try installation for long term operation) • Sales commission for distributors 		Revenue Streams <p>Fixed pricing</p> <p>Type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct sales of sensors • Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual service • Real-time transmission <p>Payment type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 22: Business Model Canvas for the Fluorescence data logger | WiSens Chl-a, designed by Damien Malarde (nke instrumentation) and WP11 Team.

Key Activities

A range of key activities, from development to post-sale technical support, are necessary to deliver this value proposition to customers. The first critical activity is **in-house developing and manufacturing** of the instruments to ensure they meet the highest performance and reliability. **Sales operations** are central, involving both direct customer engagement and coordination with the global network of agents to reach diverse markets. **Quality assurance and metrology services** play an essential role in ensuring product accuracy and compliance with industry standards. Finally, **dedicated technical support** is essential to assist customers with the deployment, maintenance, and optimal use of the data logger.

Key partnerships

A network of key partnerships is essential to ensure the success of the fluorescence data logger, as collaborations with a **few payload suppliers**. A core element of the partnership strategy is close collaboration with **marine research institutes**, which provide access to scientific expertise, real-world testing environments, and validation, ensuring alignment with the latest advancements and environmental research needs.

Cost structure

The main costs are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include expenses with **human resources** (engineering, operational and sales teams), **manufacturing infrastructures** (e.g. metrology laboratory), **basic technical support** (pre-established HR hours and guarantee). On the other hand, **variable costs** include **raw materials, parts and payload acquisition**, expenses with **calibration, testing and demonstration, marketing expenses, extra technical support** (if requested by the customer, as for first try installation for long term operation), and **sales commission for distributors**.

In continuity with the preceding Business Model Canvas analysis, the following Table 5 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process. It encompasses strategic considerations related to both product and business development, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 5: WiSens TD - Chl-a (NKE) Exploitation ID card.

FLUORESCENCE DATA LOGGER WISENS TD-CHL-A (NKE) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 1 prototype remains available for NKE for further testing (in the field and in the laboratory) <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.1 and D7.2)</small>
	Applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership NKE
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by NKE <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS and NKE); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis Several competitors <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

VI. DISSOLVED OXYGEN DATA LOGGER | WISENS TD-DO (NKE)

From the same NKE product line as WiSens TD - Chl-*a*, presented before, this **autonomous Wi-Fi-enabled underwater data logger | WISENS TD-DO** (Figure 23) is a compact, robust solution for **high-precision dissolved oxygen measurement** in both **coastal and deep-water environments**, operating at depths of **up to 600 meters**. Using luminescence quenching (**fluorescence intensity**) technology, it delivers accurate and reliable oxygen data essential for environmental monitoring, research, and marine operations. In terms of configuration, the data logger can be deployed as a **standalone unit** for data recording or **connected to a transmitter for real-time communication**. Its **compact and robust design** ensures reliable performance in aggressive and extreme environments, with integration options for use on trawlers, nets, and traps. Finally, an internal battery powers **fully autonomous operation**, enabling **flexible, long-term deployments** without external power sources.

WiSens TD - DO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000825/NAUTILOS.

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NAUTILOS

An autonomous Wi-Fi underwater datalogger for dissolved oxygen measurement down to 600 meters.

Measurable parameters	dissolved oxygen through luminescence quenching (fluorescence intensity) temperature pressure
Dissolved oxygen range	0 to 44 mg/L (± 0.1)
Temperature range	-2 to 30 °C (± 0.02)
Depth rating	600 m
Dimensions	220 x Ø45 mm
Weight (air)	393 g
Power consumption	lithium batteries (3.6 VDC)
Data Transfer	automatic via WiHub or manual via Android
Data communication protocol	Wi-Fi
Compatible	IOS, MAC OS, Windows and Android

Figure 23: Dissolved oxygen data logger | WiSens TD – DO (NKE) leaflet.

As reported in D7.1 and D7.2, the WiSens TD-DO was involved in NAUTILOS **demonstration activities in several locations** and with several collaborating partners, **essential to understand the importance of balancing between first use field support with the user experience** - an essential aspect for the commercial journey, which started already with early sales confirmed. Particularly **relevant to confirm this sensor maturity was the collaboration with CNR, starting from September 2023 and for about 2 years, where WISENS TD - DO was tested with fishermen communities** (Figure 20). Results conclude successful and regular near real time data flow and battery level check, contributed to improve maintenance protocols and to achieve TRL upgrades. It is possible to affirm that WP7 activities were essential to achieve the highest technology readiness level possible (TRL9) for **NAUTILOS WISENS TD - DO**.

As part of WP11, a thorough competitor and market analysis was conducted, resulting in a cost-benefit analysis classification for the dissolved oxygen data logger (D11.5). The data logger was classified as **“Improved Technology”**, which means that its features are considered **best fit for ocean monitoring compared with other comparable sensors** available on the market. Future plans include continuing to foster the WISENS TD–DO, which was initiated during the NAUTILOS project, **where initial unit sales have already begun**.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific technology under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented on Figure 25.

Customer segments

The dissolved oxygen data logger serves a **broad range of customer segments across the marine and freshwater domains**, each with specific needs for environmental monitoring, regulatory compliance, and sustainable resource management. Some of the specific examples below (marked with *) result from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Marine research institutions** (e.g., PNO Innovation*);
- **Marine monitoring organisations** (e.g., Sternula*, INILAB*);
- **Regulatory agencies** responsible for coastal water quality and compliance with the Water Framework Directive (WFD);
- **Environmental protection agencies** monitoring nutrient dynamics and pollution impacts in both marine and freshwater environments;
- **Drinking and wastewater treatment facilities** which depend on continuous monitoring to ensure the quality and safety of water for public use, as well as compliance with discharge regulations;
- **Local governments and regulatory bodies** evaluating freshwater quality;
- **Aquaculture and fisheries companies** (e.g., CNR, FVON).

Channels

The means through which the dissolved oxygen data logger is promoted and delivered to its customer segments include both **digital and in-person channels**. The official **websites of the NAUTILOS project and nke Instrumentation** serve as key information hubs, providing

detailed technical specifications and product updates. **NAUTILOS leaflet**, developed specifically under WP11, includes key features of the sensor and can help to communicate the sensor's value proposition to a broad audience. Additionally, **NKE's leaflet** (recently updated to include this data logger in its commercial portfolio; Figure 24), summarises the key features of the data logger and can be an important channel to promote the value proposition. Direct **business-to-business** contact plays a crucial role in building strong and tailored relationships with customers, supported by a **worldwide network of experienced sales agents** who provide localised support and extend the market reach. Additionally, it is also important to ensure a strong presence at **specialised exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows**. In that sense, the sensor was showcased in several events such as the Ocean Sciences Meeting 2024, the Oceanology International 2024, the European Maritime Day 2024, Sea Tech Week 2024 and Oceans Business 2025, either on **NAUTILOS or NKE booths** (Figure 24), where direct interactions with potential customers and new collaboration opportunities were explored, ultimately giving place to already confirmed early sales for this instrument.

Figure 24: NKE WiSens TD - DO instrument developed in NAUTILOS, showcased at NKE booths during Oceanology International 2024 (left) and Ocean Sciences Meeting 2025 (right).

Customer relationships

When it comes to building and maintaining relationships with each customer segment, constant **engagement** with customers throughout the entire process (from sales to installation) is prioritised. As part of this, **remote or on-site technical assistance** is provided whenever necessary or requested by the customer, whether to support the operation or installation of the data logger or to solve technical issues. The relationships established with customers are **highly focused on their needs and specifications**.

Revenue Streams

The dissolved oxygen data logger is available at a **fixed price**. There are various ways to possibly generate revenue from each customer segment, whether it is through **direct product sales or additional fees**, depending on customer needs. Additional fees include the possibility of contracting an **annual service, data analytics services**, the **calibration tool**, and the **real-time transmission feature**. In terms of how the customer can pay for the products, a **variable billing system** (pre or post-payment) can be considered.

Key Resources

The development and commercialisation of the dissolved oxygen data logger depend on a combination of physical, human, and intellectual resources. In terms of physical resources, the required materials include **raw materials, specialised parts and payloads**, as well as access to dedicated **production facilities**. Human resources include **production and support engineers**, who are essential for assembly and deployment, as well as **metrology engineers**, who are responsible for calibration and performance validation. A skilled **sales team** ensures effective market outreach and supports commercial partnerships.

<p>Key Partnership</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payload suppliers (e.g. sensor) • Distributors • Electronics Components Suppliers • Strong collaborative relationship with marine research institutes 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and manufacturing • Sales • Quality and Metrology services • Technical support <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical (raw materials, parts, payload and production facilities) • Workforce: Production and support engineers • Specialised engineers (e.g. for metrology) • Sales team 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An autonomous Wi-Fi underwater data logger for dissolved oxygen measurement through luminescence quenching (fluorescence intensity) in coastal and deep waters (down to 600 meters)* • Suitable to be deployed independently, either in a standalone configuration, only recording data, or connected to a transmitter • Robust, small, compact • Suitable/compliant for aggressive/extreme environment • Integrable on trawlers, nets and traps • Internal battery to provide power <p>*NAUILOS WP7 demonstration activities in the Atlantic Ocean and the Adriatic Sea</p>	<p>Customer relationship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constantly engaging with customers • Remote or on-site technical assistance • Highly customer focused <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website (NAUILOS and NKE Instrumentation) • NAUILOS sensor leaflet, NKE leaflet • NAUILOS newsletter • Personalised direct contacts (Business to business) • Worldwide network of sales agents • Specialized exhibitions, Conferences and Trade Shows (e.g. Ocean* Sciences Meeting 2024*, Oceanology International 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*) <p>*NAUILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine research (e.g. PNO Innovation Portugal*) • Marine monitoring (e.g. Sternula*, INILAB*) • Marine regulatory agencies for coastal water quality and for compliance with the WFD • Environmental Agencies • Drinking and wastewater treatment plants • Local government and regulatory authorities in relation to freshwater • Aquaculture and fisheries (e.g. CNR, FVON) <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUILOS Brokerage events</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p>Fixed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resources (engineering, operational and sales teams) • Manufacturing infrastructures (e.g. metrology laboratory) • Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and guarantee) <p>Variable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquisition of raw materials, parts and payload • Expenses with calibration, testing and demonstration • Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) • Extra technical support (if requested by the customer, e.g. first try installation for long term operation) • Sales commission for distributors 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>Fixed pricing</p> <p>Type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct sales of sensors • Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual service • Real-time transmission <p>Payment type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 25: Business Model Canvas for the Dissolved oxygen data logger | WiSens TD - DO, designed by Damien Malarde (nke instrumentation) and WP11 Team.

Key Activities

A range of key activities, from development to post-sale technical support, are necessary to deliver this value proposition to customers. The first critical activity is **in-house developing and manufacturing** of the instruments to ensure they meet the highest performance, reliability and depth capability. **Sales operations** are central, involving both direct customer engagement and coordination with the global network of agents to reach diverse markets. **Quality assurance and metrology services** play an essential role in ensuring product accuracy and compliance with industry standards. Finally, **dedicated technical support** is essential to assist customers with the deployment, maintenance, and optimal use of the data logger.

Key partnerships

The success of the dissolved oxygen data logger is supported by a strategic network of key partnerships. Collaborations with a **few payload suppliers**, including sensor manufacturers, and electronics component suppliers ensure the data logger is equipped with high-quality, mission-specific capabilities. Additionally, partnerships with **distributors** guarantee operational efficiency and effective delivery. A core element of the partnership strategy is close collaboration with **marine research institutes**, which provide access to scientific

expertise, joint research opportunities, real-world testing environments, and validation, ensuring alignment with the latest advancements and environmental research needs.

Cost structure

The main costs involved in manufacturing the dissolved oxygen data logger are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include expenses with **human resources** (engineering, operational and sales teams), **manufacturing infrastructures** (e.g., metrology laboratory), **basic technical support** (pre-established HR hours and guarantee).

On the other hand, **variable costs** include **raw materials, parts and payload acquisition**, expenses with **calibration, testing and demonstration, marketing expenses** (in particular, the organisation of exhibitions), **extra technical support** (if requested by the customer, as for first try installation for long term operation), and **sales commission for distributors**.

In continuity with the preceding Business Model Canvas analysis, the following Table 6 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process. It encompasses strategic considerations related to both product and business development, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 6: WiSens TD - DO (NKE) Exploitation ID card.

DISSOLVED OXYGEN DATA LOGGER WISENS TD-DO (NKE) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 3 units will remain available at NKE for future demonstrations activities <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.1 and D7.2)</small>
	Applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership NKE
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by NKE <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS and NKE); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis Several competitors <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Early Sales Yes

VII. FLUOROMETRIC DISSOLVED OXYGEN SENSOR (HES-SO)

While the WiSens TD - DO uses luminescence quenching (fluorescence intensity) technology, the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor developed by HES-SO (Figure 26), presented in this chapter, uses another type of luminescence quenching - **the fluorescence lifetime**. It is **based on a novel concept published by HES-SO in 2011**. NAUTILOS activities focused on designing, fabricating and testing a compact solution to fit into a NKE casing.

Fluorometric DO Sensor

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101019520 (NAUTILOS).

hes-so.ch/accueil
marco.mazza@hefr.ch

Compact and high-resolution dissolved oxygen sensor through fluorescence quenching.

Measured parameter	Dissolved oxygen through fluorescence quenching (fluorescence lifetime)
Estimated sensibility	0.001 mg/L in water (both in fresh and salt water)
Dimensions	90 x Ø20 mm
Weight (air)	177 g (including waterproof casing) – NKE WIMo sensor platform
Power supply	12 V, 70 mA average (<250 mA peak)
Communication protocols	RS-232 and RS-485 (NMEA compatible)
Depth rating	250 m

Figure 26: Fluorometric DO sensor (HES-SO) leaflet.

In the scope of NAUTILOS, the solution presented is completely new and modulated according to NKE requests, and offers a **highly compact, robust, and energy-efficient solution for aquatic monitoring**, using fluorescence quenching to achieve high-resolution measurement, compared to existing commercial alternatives. The sensor developed is a highly **flexible technology**, being **compatible with NKE data loggers, multi-parameter probes, and complex multisensor platforms such as oceanic observatories**. It can be integrated into a wide range of environmental monitoring systems, **delivering high-quality data while minimising operational costs and footprint**. As reported in D7.4, WP7 demonstrations (Figure 27) took

place in several locations whereas the HES-SO sensor performed in line with the established plan, and it went smoothly with no issues to be highlighted.

Figure 27: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the fluorometric DO sensor, in an operational environment with HES-SO fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor (more information in D7.4) with EDGELAB AUV platform in Portugal (left) or in Italy at DIAM Buoy location (right).

As part of WP11, a thorough competitor and market analysis was conducted, resulting in a cost-benefit analysis classification for the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor (D11.5). The sensor was classified as **“Cheaper in Class”**, meaning that it is the cheapest sensor on the market compared to other commercial sensors with similar characteristics.

Despite the technical performance, confirmed via NAUTILOS activities and MINKE Validation at IFREMER, **the cost-benefit analysis classification was definitely one of the main reasons why NKE confirmed to have interest in HES-SO sensor commercialisation.** This sensor cost-benefit classification, **demonstrates that even in a highly competitive market such as dissolved oxygen monitoring, cost-driven innovation is possible** - once again highlighting NAUTILOS’s significant contribution to the democratisation of marine environmental monitoring. Despite being the “cheaper in class” also has the **lowest average energy consumption, making it ideal for long-term autonomous deployments.**

Further development and the go-to-market strategy relies on the effective conclusion of a commercial agreement to be established between HES-SO and NKE. The first meeting between NKE Business and Innovation Department and HES-SO Technology Transfer Office is scheduled to happen soon. **Following this, both partners intend to continue joint development efforts to advance the system to TRL9.**

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific sensor under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure.** The final BMC is presented on Figure 28.

Customer segments

The fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor is tailored for a diverse range of customers involved in **marine and freshwater monitoring, regulation, and research**. Some of the specific examples below (marked with *) result from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Marine research institutions** (e.g., PNO Innovation*);
- **Marine monitoring organisations** (e.g., INILAB*);
- **Regulatory agencies** responsible for coastal water quality and compliance with the Water Framework Directive (WFD);
- **Environmental protection agencies** monitoring nutrient dynamics and pollution impacts in both marine and freshwater environments;
- **Drinking and wastewater treatment facilities**;
- **Local governments and regulatory bodies** evaluating freshwater quality.

Channels

Both **digital and in-person channels** are considered to effectively promote and deliver the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor. The official **website of NAUTILOS** provides detailed technical specifications and product updates. **NAUTILOS sensor leaflet**, developed specifically under WP11, includes key features of the sensor and can help to communicate the sensor's value proposition to a broad audience. **Personalised direct contacts** (e.g., business to business) are essential to build strong and tailored relationships with customers. Considering intentions to commercialise from NKE, promotion is expected to be supported by **NKE's worldwide network of experienced sales agents**. Additionally, it is also important to ensure a **strong presence at specialised exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows**. In that sense, the sensor was showcased in several events such as the European Maritime Day 2024, promoted in the scope of NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3).

Customer relationships

Considering the future commercialisation from NKE, it follows the same standard as previous NAUTILOS instruments. When it comes to building and maintaining relationships with each customer segment, **constant engagement with customers** throughout the entire process (**from sales to installation**) is prioritised. In this particular case, **whenever necessary HESSO will be also involved**, mainly during development and early sales phases. **Remote or on-site technical assistance** is provided whenever necessary or requested by the customer, whether to support the operation or installation of the sensor or to solve technical issues.

Revenue Streams

The fluorometric DO sensor is available at a **fixed price**. There are different ways to possibly earn revenue from each customer segment, whether it is through **direct product sales or additional fees**, which depend on customer needs. Additional fees include the possibility of contracting an **annual service, data analytics services, the calibration tool, and the real-time transmission feature**. In terms of how the customer can pay for the products, a **variable billing system** (pre or post-payment) can be considered.

Key Resources

The development and commercialisation of the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor depend on a combination of **physical, human, and intellectual resources**. In terms of physical

resources, the required materials include raw **materials**, **specialised parts**, and **sensor payloads**, as well as access to dedicated **production facilities**. Human resources include **production and support engineers**, who are essential for assembly and deployment, and **metrology engineers**, who are responsible for calibration and performance validation. A **skilled sales force** ensures effective market outreach, while environmental sustainability is supported by a **life cycle assessment (LCA) expert** to evaluate and minimise the sensor’s environmental footprint. Furthermore, **expertise in intellectual property (IP) management and contract negotiation** is critical to protect innovations and support commercial partnerships.

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong relationship between NKE and HESSO (NKE developing party) Components supplier Fluorophore supplier 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development and manufacturing Sales Quality and Metrology services Technical support 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compact and high-resolution dissolved oxygen sensor through fluorescence quenching Best measurement resolution compared to competitors Lowest depth rating and average energy consumption Cheapest O₂ sensor in the market Robust, small, compact Flexible technology i.e. adaptable to NKE data logger or multi-parameter probe and also possible to integrate with multisensor platform (e.g. oceanic observatory) Autonomous Cointegration with multisensor platform (e.g. oceanic observatory) <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activities in the Mediterranean Sea</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constantly engaging with customers Remote or on-site technical assistance 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine research (e.g. PNO Innovation Portugal*) Marine Monitoring (e.g. INILAB*) Marine regulatory agencies for coastal water quality and for compliance with the WFD Environmental Agencies Drinking and wastewater treatment plants Local government and regulatory authorities in relation to freshwater <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage events</p>
Cost Structure <p>Fixed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human resources (engineering, operational and sales teams) Manufacturing infrastructures (e.g. metrology laboratory) Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and guarantee) <p>Variable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquisition of raw materials, parts and payload Expenses with calibration, testing and demonstration Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) Extra technical support (if requested by the customer, e.g. first try installation for long term operation) Royalties (if applicable) 		Revenue Streams <p>Fixed pricing</p> <p>Type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct sales of sensors Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual service Data analytics Calibration tool Real-time transmission <p>Payment type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 28: Business Model Canvas for the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor, designed by Marco Mazza (HES-SO), Damien Malarde (nke instrumentation) and WP11 Team.

Key Activities

Core activities span the entire lifecycle of the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor, from development to post-sale technical support. The first critical activity is **in-house development and manufacturing** of the sensors, to ensure they meet the highest standards of performance, reliability, and depth capability. **Sales operations** are central, involving both direct customer engagement and coordination with the global network of agents to reach diverse markets. **Quality assurance and metrology services** play a critical role in guaranteeing sensor accuracy and compliance with industry standards. Finally, **dedicated technical support** is essential to assist customers with deployment, maintenance, and optimal use of the sensor.

Key partnerships

The success of the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor is supported by a strategic network of key partnerships. NKE, the sensor’s developer, collaborates closely with **HES-SO (University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland)** to drive technical innovation and validation. Additionally, partnerships with highly specialised suppliers, in particular a **dedicated fluorophore supplier**, ensure consistent access to high-quality materials essential for sensor performance and production scalability.

Cost structure

The major costs involved in manufacturing the fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include expenses with **human resources** (engineering, operational and sales teams), **manufacturing infrastructures** (e.g. metrology laboratory), and **basic technical support** (pre-established HR hours and guarantee. On the other hand, **variable costs** include **raw materials, parts and payload acquisition**, expenses with **calibration, testing and demonstration, marketing expenses** (in particular, the organisation of exhibitions), **extra technical support** (if requested by the customer, as for first try installation for long term operation), and royalties (if applicable).

In continuity with the preceding Business Model Canvas analysis, the following Table 7 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process. It encompasses strategic considerations related to both product and business development, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 7: Fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor (HES-SO) Exploitation ID card.

FLUOROMETRIC DISSOLVED OXYGEN SENSOR (HES-SO) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 2 units will remain available at HES-SO for future development activities, and 1 unit will remain available for EDGELAB deployments <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.4)</small>
	Applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership HES-SO
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets. The novel concept proposed for the fluorometric DO sensor was published in 2011
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by NKE (commercial agreement under discussion with HES-SO) <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Cheaper in Class <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis Several competitors <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

VIII. CLICK & SOUND RECORDER (AQUATEC)

AQUATE click and sound recorder (Figure 29) is a dual-function passive broadband recorder that offers a **unique and cost-effective solution for marine mammal observation and soundscape analysis**. Designed to advance scientific understanding of underwater environments, the recorder delivers **high-precision sound recording** and reliable detection of vocalising marine mammals, including a **unique capability for click-triggered recording**. The system is supported by proprietary, well-established software tools – **AQUAtalk for communication and AQUAclick View for data processing** – enhancing usability and analysis capabilities. With a strong in-house employee capability with expertise in assembly, calibration, and testing, as well as a long experience and established reputation in the marine instrumentation and marine mammal research sectors, customers are offered a **dependable and field-proven product** tailored to their specific needs.

It is important to highlight that AQUATEC click and sound recorder results from the combination of 2 project results, into one commercial product: 1) Passive broadband acoustic recording sensor for noise monitoring; 2) Passive acoustic event recorder (porpoise & dolphin clicks for abundance estimation).

Click & Sound Recorder

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 10100025 (NAUTILOS).

AQUATECGROUP.COM ENQUIRY@AQUATECGROUP.COM

A dual-function passive broadband recorder for marine mammal observation and soundscape analysis.

Hydrophone	Custom high-sensitivity hydrophone
Click recorder function	Identifies and records click events at common echolocation frequencies
Sound recorder function	Records sounds from very low frequencies of 5 Hz up to 150 kHz
Motion sensor	9-Axis module
Additional features	Temperature sensor and USB connection
Power	User rechargeable batteries
Dimensions	460 mm x 98 mm (Ø)
Weight	3.6 Kg in air, 0.79 Kg in water

Figure 29: Click and sound recorder (AQUATEC) leaflet.

In the scope of the NAUTILOS project, mostly in the scope of WP7, AQUATEC click and sound recorder was tested in various locations and integration tested in different platforms, with several collaborating partners (Figure 30). This was essential to understand the importance of balancing first use field support and users experience - an essential aspect for the commercial journey ahead. Particularly relevant to confirm this sensor's maturity was the **collaboration with Kolmården Zoo in Sweden**, that tested this sensor first in controlled conditions and afterwards connected to Swedish fishermen communities. This collaboration is intended to continue beyond NAUTILOS showing AQUATEC interest to keep on testing product maturity over time and to advance the system to TRL 9.

Figure 30: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted in operational environment (more information in D7.1 and D7.2: AQUATEC click and sound recorder at Kolmården Zoo (left) and with CEiiA's ASV (middle); datasets made available through the NAUTILOS data portal on the project website (right).

Despite this sensor's outstanding characteristics, it is offered at a price point lower than competing products, thus providing an exceptional value without compromising on performance. In the scope WP11 competitor and market analysis conducted, resulting in a cost-benefit analysis classification for the click and sound recorder (D11.5) the device was classified as **“Cheaper in Class”**.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific technology under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented on Figure 32.

Customer segments

The click and sound recorder is designed to serve several customers involved in **marine research, environmental monitoring, and blue economy sectors**. Key customer segments include:

- **Cetacean Research institutions** which require high-precision acoustic tools to monitor marine mammal presence and behaviour (e.g., Kolmården Zoo; SMRU);
- **Coastal Survey and Oceanographic Research organisations** that need reliable, high-quality soundscape data for environmental assessments (e.g., Fugro; SLU);
- **Aquaculture sector**, which can use the technology to monitor underwater noise in fishing farms (e.g. MOWI);
- **Fisheries sector** which can use the recorder to understand fish behaviour and reduce bycatch (e.g., DTU AQUA);
- **Ocean Renewable Energies** that require technologies that enable the monitoring of

- underwater acoustic impacts of infrastructure and operations (e.g., RWE);
- **Oceanic Observatories** (e.g., Portofino Marine Mammal Sanctuary) which can use this technology to contribute to long-term biodiversity monitoring and marine conservation initiatives.

Channels

The strategy employed to promote and deliver the click and sound recorder to customer segments include both **digital and in-person channels**. The official **websites of the NAUTILOS project and AQUATEC** provide detailed technical specifications and product updates. Promotional materials such as the **NAUTILOS leaflet and AQUATEC promotional material**, can be used to clearly communicate the key features and benefits of this technology to a broad audience. Then, **direct marketing**, leveraging a CRM database of **over 13,000 industry contacts built over 35 years of engagement**, plays a crucial role in building strong, tailored relationships with customers. This is supported by a **worldwide network of sales agents** providing localised support and extending the market reach. Additionally, it is also important to participate in **specialised exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows**. In that sense, the click and sound recorder was showcased in several events during the NAUTILOS project (D11.3), such as the MATS 2023 (Figure 31). Finally, active presence on **LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram** to reach a broad audience, share updates, and build brand visibility.

Figure 31: AQUATEC click and sound recorder instrument developed in NAUTILOS, showcased in MATS - Marine Autonomy & Technology Showcase 2023 in UK (left) and Ocean Sciences meeting 2024 in New Orleans (right).

Customer relationships

In terms of customer relationships, **strong and long-term relationships** with the diverse network of existing customers is maintained through **consistent engagement** ensuring their evolving needs are understood and met. A **dedicated personal approach** is prioritised, putting the customer first in all interactions, and fostering trust and loyalty. In addition, **prompt and effective technical support**, available both remotely and on-site, is guaranteed to ensure smooth operation and customer satisfaction throughout the product lifecycle.

Revenue Streams

The click and sound recorder is **available at a fixed price**, however there is a room for discount negotiation where commercially appropriate. There are various ways to possibly generate revenue from each customer segment, including:

- **Direct Sales:** products are sold directly to customers, sometimes via representatives;

- **Rentals:** product is only available for short term use in the scope of temporary or project-specific needs;
- **Support services:** ongoing revenue is supported by servicing, repair, calibration, training, data processing.

Regarding the payment type, a **variable billing system** (pre or post-payment) can be considered depending on the customer's needs.

Key Resources

The successful development and commercialisation of the click and sound recorder depend on a combination of **skilled teams, specialised facilities, and advanced software tools**. Key human resources include dedicated teams in **sales and marketing, production, and engineering & R&D**, each contributing to product development, customer engagement, and market growth. **Manufacturing facilities, calibration equipment and an acoustic test tank** are essential physical resources, ensuring precision, performance validation, and quality control throughout the production process. Finally, **software tools** are essential to support design and development activities and include AutoCAD and Solidworks for mechanical design and simulation, Altium for PCB design, and Matlab for data processing.

Key Activities

A range of key activities, spanning the entire product lifecycle, from research and development to post-sales support, are necessary to deliver this value proposition to customers. **Sales and marketing activities** focus on promoting the products, engaging with customers, managing relationships, and driving market growth. **Procurement, manufacture, and production** ensure the sourcing of quality components, efficient assembly, and reliable delivery of our instruments. **Testing and calibration** are critical to guaranteeing the performance, precision, and compliance of the systems, particularly in the demanding marine environment. **Service and repair activities** are also critical to maintain long-term functionality and customer satisfaction, along with **engineering and R&D capabilities** (expertise in electronics, mechanical, acoustic, and software engineering).

Key partnerships

A strong network of strategic partnerships is essential for the success of the click and sound recorder. Building long-term relationships with a **diverse supply chain** helps to ensure continuity of supply for critical components and materials, thereby reducing production risks. A unique collaboration with **Kolmården Zoo in Sweden**, which provides technical and trial support, enables access to captive and wild animal populations, which is a valuable resource for testing and validating acoustic monitoring technologies in the real world. Finally, a **global network of sales agents** plays a key role in expanding market access, offering local expertise and customer support across multiple regions.

Cost structure

The main costs involved in manufacturing the click and sound recorder are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include **in-house labour for manufacture**, and **amortised R&D costs**. On the other hand, **variable costs** include bought items such as **electronic components, circuit boards, machined housings, connectors and cables**.

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long term relationships with diverse supply chain, multiple sources of supply Technical and trials support and access to captive and wild animal populations from Kolmården Zoo, Sweden Worldwide network of sales agents 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sales and Marketing Production <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Procurement Manufacture Test Calibration Service and Repair Engineering & R&D <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronics Mechanical Acoustic Software 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A dual-function passive broadband recorder for marine mammal observation and soundscape analysis*. Advances understanding of the marine soundscape and the presence of vocalising marine mammals providing high precision sound recording and marine mammal click detection. Unique capability of providing click-triggered sound recording. Unique and well-established communications (AQUAtalk) and processing (AQUAclick view) software. Price point lower than competing products. Strong in-house employee capability for assembly, calibration, and test Long experience and established reputation in the marine instrumentation and marine mammal sectors. <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activity in the Baltic and Mediterranean.</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constantly engaging with our diverse network of existing customers. Dedicated personal approach, putting the customer first. Prompt and effective technical support, both remotely and on site. 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cetacean Research (e.g. Kolmården Zoo, Sweden, SMRU, UK;) Coastal Survey and Oceanographic Research (e.g. Fugro, worldwide, SLU, Sweden) Aquaculture (e.g. MOWI, UK) Fisheries (e.g. DTU AQUA) Ocean Renewable Energies (e.g. RWE, Germany) Oceanic Observatories (e.g. Portofino Marine Mammal Sanctuary)
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In-house labour for manufacture Amortised R&D costs. Variable Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bought items, including electronic components, circuit boards, machined housings, connectors and cables 		Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pricing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed Discount negotiation where commercially appropriate Type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Sales: Direct sales of instrument to customers, sometimes via representatives Rentals: For short term use Support: Servicing, Repair, Calibration, Training, Data Processing Payment type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>		

Figure 32: Business Model Canvas for the click and sound recorder, designed by Andy Smerdon (AQUATEC) and WP11 Team.

In continuity with the preceding BMC analysis, Table 8 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 8: Click and sound recorder (AQUATEC) Exploitation ID card.

CLICK & SOUND RECORDER (AQUATEC) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 1 unit will remain with Kolmården Zoo for further testing; additional prototypes will be used by AQUATEC for further development and in-house testing (for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.1 and D7.2)
	Not applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership AQUATEC
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	IPR Protection Copyright, trade secret and trademark
	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by AQUATEC (for more information, please check specific BMC above)
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS and AQUATEC); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events (for more information, please check specific D11.3)
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology (for more information, please check specific D11.5)
Competitor's analysis One single competitor (for more information, please check specific D11.5)	

IX. ACTIVE ACOUSTIC PROFILING DATA LOGGER | AQUASCAT MK2 (AQUATEC)

The active acoustic profiling data logger (Figure 33) is a **high-frequency profiling sensor** that offers a **unique and non-intrusive solution** for advanced sediment studies and marine biology research. Designed to deliver high-precision time series data, the instrument significantly enhances understanding of suspended particle dynamics across a range of environments: sediment layers, marine biota, ice, and industrial processes. It is the only **multi-frequency acoustic instrument** capable of profiling both suspended load and mean particle size on a **fine spatial and temporal grid**. The system is supported by an **advanced software system**, including AQUAtalk for communications and the AQUAscat Toolkit for data processing. In terms of cost, it is offered at a price comparable to other acoustic profiling instruments such as Doppler current profilers, however this solution delivers superior functionality without additional cost. Supported by strong in-house expertise in assembly, calibration, and testing, and developed by a team with a long experience and established reputation in the marine instrumentation sector, this technology ensures **reliable performance and scientific value**.

AQUAscat Mk2

A high-frequency profiling sensor for sediment studies and marine biology.

Measurement	Load and mean particle size
Method	Acoustic backscatter
Transducers	Up to 4 cabled transducers
Profiles	<1 m to 10 m (model dependent)
Vertical resolution	2.5 mm to 4 cm (model dependent)
Deployment	Fresh and seawater to 6 000 m depth
Autonomy	Internal batteries and memory for autonomous deployment
Sensors	Integral temperature and pressure sensors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 10100625 (NAUTILOS).

AQUATECGROUP.COM ENQUIRY@AQUATECGROUP.COM

Figure 33: Active acoustic profiling data logger (AQUATEC) leaflet.

As reported in D7.4, the active acoustic profiling data logger was **deployed successfully in Portugal**, after a successful integration on **CEiiA's Lander** (Figure 34). WP7 results presented demonstrate a significant improvement in the sensor's performance. **A successful correlation between acoustic profiles and visual data was achieved, after a 48 hour mission underwater, including the detection of a fish by both instruments** - enabling an estimation of the distance between the fish and the equipment. From the technical performance perspective, the sampler prototype functioned well in a realistic environment, meeting all operational requirements during the field test.

Figure 34: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the active acoustic profiling data logger, in an operational environment (more information in D7.4): Active acoustic profiling data logger in Portugal, with CEiiA's Lander (left), detection of a fish by both instruments (middle); CEiiA and AQUATEC teams working together, after deployment.

The first prototype commercial instrument will be in production by the end of the project. As soon as this is validated, it is expected to interact with potential customers including those identified in NAUTILOS brokerage events through sales and marketing activities. This will include a product launch at a venue to be determined, and presentation at forthcoming exhibitions and conferences after the project, including Particles in Europe (Oostende, Belgium, Sep 25), Ocean Sciences Meeting (Glasgow, UK, Feb 26) and Oceanology International (London, UK, March 26).

As part of WP 11, a thorough competitor and market analysis was conducted, resulting in a cost-benefit analysis classification for the active acoustic profiling data logger (D11.5). The device was classified as **"Improved Technology and Cheaper in Class"**, meaning that, compared with market competitors, its benefits and technical features are considered best fit for ocean monitoring, and it has a lower cost.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific technology under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented in Figure 35 and serves as the starting point for the work to be further discussed during the BOOSTER initiative.

Customer segments

The active acoustic profiling data logger is designed to serve several customers involved in **marine research, environmental monitoring, and blue economy sectors**. Some of the specific

examples below (marked with *) result from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Coastal Survey and Oceanographic Research Institutions** that study suspended sediment dynamics, water column structure, and ecosystem processes (e.g., Fugro, RPS, Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale, East China Normal University, PNO Innovation*, INILAB*);
- **Oceanic Observatories and Government Research Bodies** (e.g., US Geological Survey, National Oceanography Centre UK, National Research Council Canada);
- **Polar Research Institutions** which study ice particle interactions and sediment dynamics in polar environments (e.g., British Antarctic Survey, Université Laval);
- **Aquaculture sector**, that requires monitoring of suspended solids and particle concentrations impacting farm environments and stock health (e.g., MOWI);
- **Ocean Renewable Energies** that need to assess sediment transport, turbidity, and environmental impacts of offshore infrastructure (e.g., RWE);
- **Deep Ocean Research Organisations** for profiling particulate matter in deep-sea ecosystems and supporting marine geology research (e.g., RBINS).

Channels

The strategy employed to promote and deliver the AQUAscat Mk2 to customer segments include both digital and in-person channels. The official **websites of the NAUTILOS project and AQUATEC** provide detailed technical specifications and product updates. Promotional materials such as the **NAUTILOS leaflet**, can be used to clearly communicate the key features and benefits of this technology to a broad audience. Then, **direct marketing**, leveraging a CRM database of over **13,000 industry contacts built over 35 years** of engagement, plays a crucial role in building strong, tailored relationships with customers. This is supported by a **worldwide network of sales agents** providing localised support and extending the market reach. Additionally, it is also important to participate in specialised **exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows**. In that sense, the AQUAscat Mk2 was showcased in several exhibitions promoted in the scope of NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3), such EMD 2024, and Sea Tech Week 2024 (broad) and Particles in Europe (more focused for the targeted customers), where direct interactions with potential customers and new collaboration opportunities were explored. NAUTILOS also ensured the presence in the Ocean Sciences conference (broad) and the Coastal Sediments conference (focused) to engage with researchers and stakeholders interested in this technology. Finally, active presence on **LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram** to reach a broad audience and build brand visibility.

Customer relationships

In terms of customer relationships, **strong and long-term relationships** with the diverse network of existing customers is maintained through **consistent engagement** ensuring their evolving needs are understood and met. A **dedicated personal approach** is prioritised, putting the customer first in all interactions, and fostering trust and loyalty. In addition, we offer **prompt and effective technical support**, available both remotely and on-site, to ensure smooth operation and customer satisfaction throughout the product lifecycle.

Revenue Streams

The AQUAscat Mk2 is available at a **fixed price**, however there is a room for discount negotiation where commercially appropriate. There are various ways to possibly generate

revenue from each customer segment, including: **Direct Sales**: products are sold directly to customers, sometimes via representatives; **Rentals**: product is only available for short term use in the scope of temporary or project-specific needs; **Support services**: ongoing revenue is supported by servicing, repair, calibration, training, data processing. Regarding the payment type, a **variable billing system** (pre or post-payment) can be considered depending on the customer's needs.

Key Resources

The successful development and commercialisation of AQUAscat Mk2 depends on a combination of skilled teams, specialised facilities, and advanced software tools. Key **human resources** include dedicated teams in **sales and marketing, production, and engineering & R&D**, each contributing to product development, customer engagement, and market growth. **Manufacturing facilities, calibration equipment** and an **acoustic test tank** are essential physical resources, ensuring precision, performance validation, and quality control throughout the production process. On the intellectual property side, **relevant patents** on signal processing techniques granted and the **AQUAscat trademark** are essential to protect our technological innovations and brand identity. Finally, **software tools** are essential to support design and development activities and include AutoCAD and Solidworks for mechanical design and simulation, Altium for PCB design, and Matlab for data processing.

Key Activities

A range of key activities, spanning the entire product lifecycle is necessary to deliver this value proposition to customers. **Sales and marketing activities** focus on promoting the products, engaging with customers, managing relationships, and driving market growth. **Procurement, manufacture, and production** ensure the sourcing of quality components, efficient assembly, and reliable delivery of our instruments. **Testing and calibration** are critical to guaranteeing the performance, precision, and compliance of the systems, particularly in the demanding marine environment. **Service and repair activities** are also critical to maintain long-term functionality and customer satisfaction. Finally, **engineering and R&D capabilities** (electronics, mechanical, acoustic, and software engineering) sustain innovation and continuous product improvement.

Key partnerships

A strong network of strategic partnerships is essential for the success of the AQUAscat Mk2. A key partner is the **University of Aberdeen (UK)**, which provides ongoing academic and facilities support through AQUATEC-funded PhD research (led by Andy Smerdon, AQUATEC) contributing to the continued development and refinement of the technologies. Finally, a **global network of sales agents** plays a key role in expanding market access, offering local expertise and customer support across multiple regions, and strengthening our presence in the marine and environmental instrumentation sectors.

Cost structure

The main costs involved in manufacturing the active acoustic profiler are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include **in-house labour for manufacture, and amortised R&D costs**. On the other hand, **variable costs** include bought items such as **electronic components**.

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long term relationships with diverse supply chain, multiple sources of supply Ongoing academic and facilities support from University of Aberdeen (UK) for technology development through Aquatec-funded PhD studies (Andy Smerdon) Worldwide network of sales agents 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sales and Marketing Production <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Procurement Manufacture Test Calibration Service and Repair Engineering & R&D <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronics Mechanical Acoustic Software Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teams: Sales & Marketing; Production; Engineering & R&D Facilities: Manufacturing, Calibration equipment, Acoustic test tank IP: Patents & AQUAscet trademark Software: AutoCAD and Solidworks for mechanical design and simulation, Altium for PCB design, Matlab for processing 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A high-frequency profiling sensor for sediment studies and marine biology* Advances understanding of suspended particle dynamics in sediment, marine biota, ice, and industrial processes by providing non-intrusive, high precision particle size and load time series. The only multi-frequency instrument capable of determining profiles of suspended load, and mean particle size. Unique and well-established communications (AQUAtalk) and processing (AQUAscet Toolkit) software. Price comparable with other acoustic profiling instruments such as Doppler current profilers Strong in-house employee capability for assembly, calibration, and test Long experience and established reputation in the marine instrumentation sector. <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activity in the Atlantic Ocean</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constantly engaging with our diverse network of existing customers. Dedicated personal approach, putting the customer first. Prompt and effective technical support, both remotely and on site. Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Websites (NAUTILOS/ AQUATEC) NAUTILOS sensor leaflet NAUTILOS newsletter Direct marketing (CRM database with 13,000 industry contacts that we dealt with over the last 35 years) Worldwide network of sales agents Exhibitions - broad (e.g. Oceanology, EMD 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*) and focused (e.g. Particles in Europe) Conferences - broad (e.g. Ocean Sciences) and focused (e.g. Coastal Sediments) Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coastal Survey and Oceanographic Research (e.g. Fugro, RPS, INILAB*, Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale, France, East China Normal University, PNO Innovation Portugal**) Oceanic Observatories (e.g. US Geological Survey, National Oceanography Centre, UK, National Research Council, Canada) Polar Research (e.g. British Antarctic Survey, Université Laval, Canada) Aquaculture (e.g. MOWI, UK) Ocean Renewable Energies (e.g. RWE, Germany) Deep Ocean Research (e.g. RBINS, Belgium) <p>**Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage events</p>
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In-house labour for manufacture Amortised R&D costs. Variable Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bought items, including electronic components, circuit boards, machined housings, connectors and cables 		Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pricing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed Discount negotiation where commercially appropriate Type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Sales: Direct sales of instrument to customers, sometimes via representatives Rentals: For short term use Support: Servicing, Repair, Calibration, Training, Data Processing Payment type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 35: Business Model Canvas for the active acoustic profiling data logger | AQUAscet Mk 2, designed by Andy Smerdon (AQUATEC) and WP11 Team.

In continuity with the preceding BMC analysis, the following Table 9 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 9: Active acoustic profiling data logger | AQUAscet Mk 2 (AQUATEC) Exploitation ID card.

ACTIVE ACOUSTIC PROFILING DATA LOGGER AQUASCAT MK2 (AQUATEC) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 1 prototype, available for AQUATEC for further development and in-house testing (for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.4)
	Not applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership AQUATEC
	IPR Protection Copyright, patents granted, trademark registered and trade secret
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by AQUATEC (for more information, please check specific BMC above)
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events (for more information, please check specific D11.3)
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology (for more information, please check specific D11.5)
	Competitor's analysis Several competitors (for more information, please check specific D11.5)

X. SUBMERSIBLE SAMPLER FOR NANOPLASTICS AND MICROPLASTICS (SubCTech)

The submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics (Figure 36) consists of a **robust, automated deepwater sampling solution** designed to meet the growing need for accurate, long-term monitoring of microplastic and nanoplastic pollution in marine environments. It offers the possibility of **automatic, programmable sampling schedules** via a display control unit, enabling **deployments of over six months at depths of up to 600 meters**, which makes it adapted for integration into existing offshore monitoring systems. The submersible sampler is **reusable, durable**, and designed for **easy handling and recharging**. With four cascade filters featuring **three distinct mesh sizes** (300 μm , 100 μm , and 30 μm - particle size) and an integrated pump (scalable up to 16 samples and other mesh sizes), it ensures **high-precision sampling**. Its **configuration is customizable** according to specific applications and user needs, which makes this solution a powerful tool for customers seeking reliable, high-resolution data on plastic pollution in the ocean.

Submersible Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000825 (NAUILOS).

subctech.com fahning@subctech.com

Submersible and automated deep water sampler for nanoplastic and microplastic particles, featuring pre-programable sampling schedules.

Parameters	Collection of nanoplastic and microplastic particles Flow rate & sample volume (other parameters optional)
Type of sampling	4 cascade filters with 3 different mesh sizes (300 μm , 100 μm and 30 μm - particle size) using an integrated pump (scalable up to 16 samples and other mesh sizes)
Depth rating	600 m
Mission duration	½ year
Power	Rechargeable Li-Ion battery
Data	Logged internally Easy data download after deployment via USB
Mission planning	Automatic sampling with user programmed timers via display control unit
Dimensions (H x W x D)	850 x 350 x 350 mm
Weight (air)	55 Kg

Figure 36: Submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics (SubCTech) leaflet.

As reported in D7.4, SubCTech submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics was **deployed in the Mediterranean Sea, on HCMR mooring line at 400 m** (Figure 37). This WP7 successful demonstration aimed to show the ability to sample pre-programmed samples (4 samples, every 20 days) as well as to measure volume flow rates. This demonstration action - made possible through the NAUTILOS project and with support from the European Union - demonstrates that, from a technical performance perspective, the sampler prototype functioned well in a realistic environment, meeting all operational requirements during the field test. Further development is planned internally at SubCTech to advance the system to TRL 9, as commercialisation efforts are already underway.

Figure 37: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the with submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics, in an operational environment (more information in D7.4): deployment for the HCMR mooring line at 400 m (left); location on the Mediterranean Sea (right).

The sampler was classified as **“Improved Technology”** (D11.5) under the competitor and market analysis that was conducted, which means that its features are considered best fit for ocean monitoring compared with other comparable sensors available on the market.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific sampler under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented on Figure 40.

Customer segments

The primary customer segments of the submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics include the following, with some of them (marked with *) resulting from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Universities and Research centers** that study anthropogenic debris in coastal zones, estuaries, and open ocean (e.g., University of Vigo*);
- **Civil protection and regulatory bodies** (Environment/atmospheric/oceanic authorities/agencies) that use this type of data to inform policy, manage incidents, and enforce environmental regulations;
- **Not-for-profit environmental organisations** and other initiatives (e.g., KIMO International*, Seaglow*) dedicated to protecting marine ecosystems are also key users of our solutions.

Channels

The customers are engaged through a combination of **digital platforms, direct outreach, events, and partnerships**. Online presence is maintained through the **NAUTILOS and SubCTech websites**, as well as **social media**, particularly LinkedIn, used actively to share updates, promote activities, and interact with the marine science and environmental communities. Promotional materials such as the **NAUTILOS sampler leaflet** (Figure 36) and **SubCTech leaflet** (Figure 38 and Figure 39), along with regular newsletters like the **NAUTILOS newsletter**, help maintain visibility and inform stakeholders of ongoing developments regarding the sampler. The **participation in key events** such as Oceanology International 2024, European Maritime Day (EMD) 2024, and Sea Tech Week 2024 was promoted in the scope of NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3), to engage directly with researchers, regulators, and potential clients. A **network of worldwide sales partners** facilitates market penetration and local customer support, while **word-of-mouth recommendations from previous customers** contribute to ongoing growth. Finally, **personalised communication** via email, telephone, and meetings allows for tailored engagement and strong relationship building.

Figure 38: SubCTech leaflet showing the SubCTech sampler (left) and Jana Fahning (SubCTech representative) at NAUTILOS booth presenting the SubCTech sampler during the European Maritime Day in Denmark (2024).

Figure 39: Close look on the submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics displayed on SubCTech company merchandising, showing that commercialisation efforts are already underway.

Customer relationships

The promotion of strong and long-term collaboration with our customers by offering **dedicated personal assistance** tailored to their specific needs is a key priority. This support is available both **on-site and remotely**, ensuring flexibility and responsiveness. This commitment extends beyond the initial engagement, with comprehensive **after-sales support** and **prompt technical assistance** designed to maintain customer satisfaction and operational reliability.

Revenue Streams

The submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics is available at a **fixed price**. There are various ways to generate revenue from each customer segment, whether it is through **direct product sales or additional fees**, depending on customer needs. **Additional fees** can be charged for on-site installation support, product customisation, and extra or long-term technical support. In terms of payment, a **variable billing system** (pre- or post-payment) can be considered.

Key Resources

This value proposition is based on a combination of **physical, human, and technical resources**. These include **raw materials** and specialised **payload components and parts**, supported by access to **advanced production facilities**. A skilled **engineering team** is responsible for designing, developing and customising the products to ensure they meet the specific needs of each customer segment. **Dedicated support technicians** provide technical expertise and maintenance, while the **sales team** plays a crucial role in customer acquisition, relationship management, and market expansion.

Key Activities

To operate successfully, the core activities of **design, manufacturing and technical support provision** are essential, including **on-site installation and remote assistance**, to ensure optimal performance and user satisfaction. **Marketing and sales efforts** focus on reaching target customer segments through digital channels, events, and direct outreach. Finally, **continuous product customisation and improvement**, based on user feedback, are essential to maintain competitiveness and address specific environmental challenges.

Key partnerships

The success of the sampler is supported by a strategic network of key partnerships. Collaboration with **laboratories specialising in microplastic analysis** provide essential scientific validation capabilities. Additionally, **long-term clients** play a key role not only as users but also as feedback partners for continuous product improvement. Collaboration with a few production suppliers ensure the reliable delivery of high-quality components and materials required for manufacturing. Finally, **worldwide sales partners** support international distribution, localised customer engagement, and business development across diverse regions.

Cost structure

The main costs involved in manufacturing the SubCTech sampler are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include **expenses with human resources** (engineering, production and operational), **infrastructures** (e.g. offices, testing labs) and **basic technical support** (pre-established HR hours and guarantee).

On the other hand, **variable costs** include **raw materials, parts and payload acquisition**, expenses with **testing and demonstration**, **marketing** expenses (in particular, the organisation of exhibitions), **on-site installation support**, **extra technical support** (if requested by the customer, as for first try installation for long term operation), and costs for **product customisation** (if requested by the customer).

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laboratories for Microplastic Analysis Long term clients Production suppliers Worldwide Sales partners 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design and manufacturing Technical support provision (e.g. on-site installation) Marketing and sales Customization/improvement Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw materials, payload, parts, production facilities Engineering team for design and customization Support technicians Sales team 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Submersible and automated deepwater sampler for nanoplastic and microplastic particles, featuring pre-programmable sampling schedules Automatic sampling with user programmed timers via display control unit, lasting over 6 months and up to 600 m (thus adapted for integration in offshore monitoring systems*) Reusable and durable solution, with easy handling and recharging 4 cascade filters with 3 different mesh sizes (300 µm, 100 µm and 30 µm - particle size) using an integrated pump (scalable up to 16 samples and other mesh sizes) Customizable based on users needs <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activity in the Mediterranean Sea, on HCMR buoy</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicated personal assistance (on-site or remote) After sales support and prompt technical assistance (on-site or remote) Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website (NAUTILOS and SCT) NAUTILOS sampler leaflet; SCT leaflet NAUTILOS newsletter Social media (e.g. SCT and NAUTILOS LinkedIn) Specialized fairs, conferences and trade shows (e.g. Oceanology International 2024, EMD 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*) Worldwide sales partners Word of mouth from previous customers Personalized direct contacts (e.g. email, telephone, meetings) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities and Research centers that study anthropogenic debris in coastal zones, estuaries, and open ocean (e.g. University of Vigo*) Civil protection and regulatory bodies (Environment/atmospheric/oceanic authorities/agencies) Not-for profit environmental organisations and other initiatives (e.g. KIMO International*, Seaglow*) <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage events</p>
Cost Structure <p>Fixed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human resources (engineering, production, operational) Infrastructures (offices, workshops, testing labs) Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and 2-year guarantee) <p>Variable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquisition of raw materials, parts and payload Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) Expenses with testing and demonstration On-site installation support Extra/long-term technical support (if requested by the customer) 		Revenue Streams <p>Fixed pricing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Product sales Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-site installation support Extra/long-term technical support Product customization Payment type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 40: Business Model Canvas for the submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics, designed by Jana Fahning (SubCTech) and WP11 Team.

In continuity with the preceding Business Model Canvas analysis, the following Table 10 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process. It encompasses strategic considerations related to both product and business development, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 10: Submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics (SubCTech) Exploitation ID card.

SUBMERSIBLE SAMPLER FOR NANOPLASTICS AND MICROPLASTICS (SubCTech) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 1 developed prototype, available for SubCTech for further tests and development <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.4)</small>
	Applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership 100% SubCTech
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by SubCTech <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS and SubCTech); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis One single competitor <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

XI. DEEP OCEAN CTD INSTRUMENT / CT SENSOR (UL-FE)

This deep ocean CTD instrument (Figure 41) offers a **cost-effective and innovative solution** for collecting oceanographic data at **depths of up to 2,000 meters**. At its core is a **novel conductivity and temperature (CT) sensor developed by UL-FE** (Figure 41), an institution with vast experience in sensor development. The **low-cost CT sensor** is built using advanced MEMS (micro-electromechanical system) technology, which allows both conductivity and temperature elements to be integrated on a **single electronic board**. This integration reduces internal electrical connections - resulting in fewer points of failure, **greater reliability**, and **lower production and maintenance costs** compared to traditional designs.

Deep Ocean CTD Sensor

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CTD sensor for measuring oceanic data up to 2 000 meters.

Measurable parameters	conductivity pressure temperature
Conductivity range	4 to 70 mS/cm (± 0.01)
Temperature range	0 to 40 °C (± 0.01)
Depth rating	2 000 m
Dimensions	3 350 x Ø120 mm
Weight (air)	15.6 kg
Input voltage	5 to 16.5 V DC
Power consumption	0.25 - 0.75 W (alone in continuous mode)
Communication protocols	RS-485

Figure 41: Deep ocean CTD instrument / CT sensor (UL-FE) leaflet.

As reported in D7.4, the CTD instrument was deployed after a successful **integration on CEiiA's Lander** (Figure 42). **Several tests were carried (at the lab, marina and offshore) for over one year**. A significant data quality improvement was achieved from October 2023 to April 2024, with **several results 100% compliant**. However, during deep deployment the CTD unexpectedly stopped responding. Further testing is needed to determine the cause, as this

appears to be an isolated incident. From the technical performance perspective, the sampler prototype functioned well in a realistic environment, however **additional offshore demonstrations are necessary** and both teams remain available in continuing testing efforts, should further funding opportunities become available.

Figure 42: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the deep ocean CTD instrument, in an operational environment (more information in D7.4): offshore operation with the Portuguese Navy on the Atlantic Ocean with CEiA's lander (left, middle); coastal missions' location, in Portugal (right).

The deep ocean CTD instrument was classified as **“Cheaper in Class”** (D11.5) under the competitor and market analysis that was conducted. This means that its performance is similar to that of other comparable sensors on the market, but at a lower cost. This sensor cost-benefit classification **demonstrates that even in a highly competitive market such as CTD monitoring, cost-driven innovation is possible** - once again highlighting NAUTILOS's significant contribution to the democratisation of marine environmental monitoring.

In parallel with the technical activities with CTD instrument in the scope of WP7, the **CT Sensor in particular caught the interest from AQUATEC** (NAUTILOS partner), willing to integrate this sensor into their proprietary solutions, as also from another **external partner from Slovenia** (EMA Group) after a conference talk at SLO-chip 2024 from Matej Mozek (UL-FE). This represented an unexpected but positive deviation from the Grant Agreement contributing to **expand applicability** and enhancing systems **cost-effective performance** across various marine and environmental contexts. In fact, this is the reason why this project result is considered a KER, once no commercial partnership was found for the CTD instrument.

At this stage, and with the goal set for 2029, **CT sensors are being developed and sold by UL-FE**. For the future a dedicated CT sensor manufacturer based in Portugal has been engaged to explore the possibility of collaborating on large-scale production, after a first interaction between NAUTILOS TIM and the Technology Transfer Office at the University of Ljubljana where more details need to be discussed, with a possible in-person visit to be planned. Concerning the integration of CT sensors on other companies' proprietary solutions, considering the **majority of knowledge available in the public domain** (through the scientific paper), discussions are taking place between partners.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific sensor under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented on Figure 43.

Customer Segments

Potential customers for the CTD instrument and CT sensor, with some of them (marked with *) resulting from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3), include:

- **Marine Research companies** (e.g., INILAB* and PNO Innovation*) working in the areas of deep ocean research and oceanic observatories;
- **Monitoring agencies (public);**
- **Private companies** developing solutions for monitoring marine and coastal environments applied to fisheries, aquaculture, and offshore industries (e.g., **AQUATEC**, also identified under NAUTILOS activities).

Channels

The customers are engaged through a combination of digital platforms, direct outreach, and events. Online presence is maintained through the **NAUTILOS and UL-FE websites**, which provide general information about the instrument and sensor. Promotional materials such as the **NAUTILOS leaflet** (Figure 41), along with scientific publications (Možek, M., Pečar, B., & Vrtačnik, D., 2024), help maintain visibility and inform stakeholders of ongoing developments regarding the Deep Ocean CTD and CT sensor. **Direct contact** with customers also plays a critical role and allows for tailored engagement and strong relationship building. The **participation in specialised fairs, conferences and trade shows**, such as the 2nd Slovenian conference on chips and semiconductors (SLO-chip 2024) to engage directly with potential clients. As a result of this second conference, **a collaboration was initiated with the EMA Group, with whom joint development activities are currently underway.**

Customer Relationship

In terms of customer relationships, it is considered essential to provide customers with **dedicated personal assistance**, and **prompt technical support**, either remote or on-site.

Revenue Streams

There are different ways to possibly earn revenue with this value proposition, whether it is through **direct product sales or additional fees**, such as **extra/long-term technical support**, which depends on customer needs. In terms of how the customer can pay for the products, a **variable billing system** (pre or post-payment) can be considered.

Key Resources

To be able to produce the CTD instrument, or the CT sensor, a combination of critical materials, human resources, and infrastructure resources are necessary. These include **essential raw materials such as electronic components**, specialised parts like **instrument housings**, and **scientific payloads** used in the sensor systems. The operations are made under dedicated **manufacturing facilities** that support the efficient assembly, integration, and testing the technologies. A team of **skilled engineers** plays a central role in product development and innovation, ensuring that technologies remain at the forefront of marine instrumentation. Complementing this, an **experienced sales team** is responsible for market engagement, customer relationship management, and driving commercial success.

Key Activities

Key activities include the **manufacturing and assembly** of CTD instruments and CT sensors, which are supported by **dedicated engineering and R&D functions**. These efforts rely on expertise in **electronics and software development** to enable continuous innovation and system integration. Each CT sensor is individually **calibrated** to ensure high accuracy and reliability. Other core activities include **sales operations** for market engagement and customer acquisition, as well as the **provision of technical support** to assist with deployment, user training, and ongoing system performance.

Key Partnerships

Strategic partnerships are essential for the success of this value proposition. Key partners include suppliers of **mechanical parts such as housings**, essential for the production of CTD instruments. At this stage, and with the goal set for 2029, **CT sensors are being developed and sold by UL-FE**. However, a dedicated CT sensor manufacturer based in Portugal has been engaged to explore the possibility of collaborating on large-scale production. Discussions between potential partners are ongoing, with mediation and support from the NAUTILOS TIM. As previously discussed, during NAUTILOS technical activities, the **CT Sensor in particular caught the interest from NAUTILOS partners**, willing to integrate this sensor into their proprietary solutions. For this reason, the business plan development also adds key partnerships, key collaborations with partners focused on developing monitoring solutions.

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw materials, parts (e.g. housing), payload suppliers CT sensor producer (for large scale production) Partners for developing monitoring solutions for the CT sensor 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturing Engineering & R&D <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electronics Software Calibration of the CT sensors (individually) Sales Technical support provision Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw materials (e.g. electronics), parts (e.g. housing), payload Manufacturing facilities Engineers (developers) Sales teams 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CTD instrument for measuring oceanic data up to 2 000 meters* An innovative and low-cost CT sensor developed by an institution with vast experience in sensors development Conductivity and temperature sensor fabricated using MEMS (micro-electromechanical system) technology, allowing for its integration on the same electronic board. Due to the reduction of internal electrical connections (one chip with a single PCB connection and thus fewer points of possible failure) it is more reliable and with more cost-effective production and maintenance. <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activities in the Atlantic Ocean</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicated personal assistance Prompt technical support (remote or on-site) Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website (NAUTILOS, UL-FE) NAUTILOS sensor leaflet NAUTILOS newsletter Direct contact Specialized fairs, conferences and trade shows (e.g. Electronica 2024 Munchen*, Semicon 2024 Munchen*, EMD 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*, SLO-chip 2024) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine research (NILAB*, PNO Innovation Portugal*) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deep ocean Oceanic observatories Monitoring agencies (public) Private companies developing solutions for monitoring marine and coastal environment applied to fisheries, aquaculture, and offshore industries (e.g. AQUATEC*) <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>
Cost Structure <p>Fixed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human resources (engineering and sales teams) Manufacturing infrastructures (e.g. laboratory for CT sensor) <p>Variable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquisition of raw materials, parts (e.g. housing) and payload (e.g. housing), payload Calibration of the sensors (individually) and demonstration Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) Royalties (if applicable) 		Revenue Streams <p>Fixed pricing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Product sales Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extra/long-term technical support Payment type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 43: Business Model Canvas for the Deep Ocean CTD Instrument, designed by Danilo Vrtačnik (UL FE) and WP11 Team.

Cost Structure

All the elements described in the sections above lead to the cost structure, which is divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include costs related to **human resources**, including **engineering and sales teams**, and investments in **manufacturing infrastructure**, such as **laboratories** dedicated to CT sensor production and testing. On the other hand, **variable costs** include the purchase of **raw materials, mechanical parts** (such as housings) and **payload** required for assembly. Additional variable expenses arise from the **individual calibration of CT sensors, demonstration activities, and marketing** efforts, including participation in exhibitions and promotional events. **Royalties** may also apply depending on the terms of intellectual property licensing or technology partnerships.

In continuity with the preceding Business Model Canvas analysis, the following Table 11 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process. It encompasses strategic considerations related to both product and business development, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

It is important to note that both socio-economic impact analyses (D11.5) were conducted based solely on the CTD instrument, as the commercial potential of the standalone CT sensor was only identified at a later stage. This represented an unexpected but positive deviation from the original Grant Agreement. WP11 teams advised UL-FE to proceed with them afterwards, despite the current interest from external partners.

Table 11: Deep ocean CTD instrument and CT sensor (UL-FE) Exploitation ID card.

DEEP OCEAN CTD INSTRUMENT / CT SENSOR (UL-FE) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 1 CTD instrument available for UL-FE for further testing. Additional CT sensors available for multiple uses. <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.4)</small>
	Interest to discuss freshwater exploitation
	IPR Ownership UL-FE
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets. The novel concept proposed for the deep ocean CTD instrument / CT sensor was published in 2024.
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy Only for CT sensor, with multiple partners (joint initiatives ongoing) <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology and Cheaper in Class (for CTD instrument; CT sensor not performed) <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis Several competitors (for CTD instrument; CT sensor not performed) <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

XII. DEEP OCEAN RADIOACTIVITY SENSOR (HCMR)

The **deep ocean radioactivity sensor** (Figure 44) is an **in-situ underwater gamma-ray spectrometer** designed for **deep ocean monitoring up to 3000 meters**. This instrument fills a critical gap in the surveillance of radioactivity levels by enabling **continuous, high-precision monitoring of radioactive substances**. It serves as a powerful tool for **detecting and assessing anthropogenic hazards** (e.g., nuclear contamination) and **natural geophysical hazards** (due to earthquakes and submarine volcanic activity), through advanced analysis methods. The spectrometer also supports the exploitation of natural mining resources by detecting radon gas and other geologically significant radioactive materials from the Earth's crust. Its smart service capabilities provide not only raw data but also analysed results and site characterisation based on contamination levels. **Reliable, easy to use and adaptable to multiple applications**, the system can be integrated across various platforms and deployment methods. It enables radioactivity profiling along depth, and when correlated with CTD data, helps identify distinct water masses and their transport pathways. With a **long deployment duration of up to 25 days**, it offers extended observation capabilities.

Deep ocean radioactivity sensor

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000026 (NAUTILOS).

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Underwater in-situ gamma-ray spectrometer for the deep ocean.

Parameters	Gamma-ray emitters (radionuclides)
Energy resolution	-7.5 % (at 661 keV 137 Cs)
Temperature range	-10 to 150 °C
Depth rating	3 000 m
Dimensions	42 x Ø15 cm
Weight (air)	15.3 kg
Input voltage	5-18 V DC
Power consumption	- 2.2 W (Operating mode)
Power autonomy	If needed a battery capacity of 120 Ah provides 25 days continuous operation
Data storage	Logged internally
Data communication protocol	USB and WI-Fi / ethernet and WI-Fi

Figure 44: Deep ocean radioactivity sensor (HCMR) leaflet.

As reported in D7.4, HCMR deep ocean radioactivity sensor was deployed in the **Cretan, Ionian and Aegean Seas**, considering different testing scenarios, including a **deep deployment up to 2100 meters** (the deepest deployment from all NAUTILOS instruments). Based on the technical challenges encountered during the demonstration phase, the sensor underwent a series of upgrades. This commercial product from NAUTILOS initially planned without data logging capabilities, concluded NAUTILOS innovation journey as a **prototype successfully tested in real operational environments with data logging capabilities and multiple offshore demonstrations** (Figure 45). The final deployment took place during the **2025 Santorini seismic crisis**, at the Kolumbo submarine volcano, challenging the sensor to **extreme environmental conditions**. The successful performance in these scenarios confirms the system’s readiness. Further development efforts are focused on initiating the commercialisation pathway, beginning with participation in the BOOSTER programme, as described below.

Figure 45: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the deep ocean radioactivity sensor, in an operational environment (more information in D7.4): deployment at sea (left) and datasets made available through the NAUTILOS data portal on the project website (right).

The deep ocean radioactivity sensor was classified as **“Improved Technology and Cheaper in Class”** (D11.5) under the competitor and market analysis that was conducted, which means that, compared with market competitors, its benefits and technical features are considered best fit for ocean monitoring, and it has a lower cost.

As soon as this technology demonstrated its operational capability and reliability, commercialisation efforts started. **HCMR is a non-profit public research body** and for that reason **commercialisation needs to happen through an external partner**. In order to discuss **technology licensing processes** and support HCMR considering **scouting for interested partners**, an **in-person visit** took place between Catarina Lemos (NAUTILOS TIM; CEiiA) and Christos Tsabaris (HCMR), in November 2023 (Figure 46). Discussions continued during monthly one-to-one meetings, **leading to the confirmation of commercialisation interest from HORST Ltd, a Greek SME** (external to NAUTILOS consortium).

HORST Ltd is a high-tech company with expertise in the design, manufacture, technological development and system installation of observing systems in the monitoring of physical, biological and anthropogenic activities at the sea. The company also provides products and

services worldwide and participates in several international R&D programs and research proposals.

Further activities with HCMR, in the scope of NAUTILOS, **always took in consideration HORST's direct contribution:**

- to perform competitor and market analysis;
- to define terms for knowledge transfer between both partners (100% Intellectual property rights belong to HCMR);
- to develop the deep ocean radioactivity sensor Business Model Canvas (see below);
- to schedule BOOSTER participation, once this instrument is included in NAUTILOS TOP3 for BOOSTER initiative;
- to submit a joint proposal for additional funding to advance this instrument to a commercial TRL.

Figure 46: Evidence from WP11 exploitation activities between CEiIA, HCMR and HORST: in-person visit to HCMR headquarters with Christos Tsabaris (HCMR) and Catarina Lemos (CEiIA), in November 2023 (left). Business Model Canvas Development between HCMR, HORST and WP11 Team in January 2024 (right).

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the BMC for the specific sensor under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC is presented in Figure 47 and serves as the starting point for the work to be **further discussed during the BOOSTER initiative**.

Customer segments

The underwater in-situ gamma-ray spectrometer targets a **diverse range of customer segments** across research, industry, and public sectors. Some of the specific examples below (marked with *) result from direct contacts during NAUTILOS brokerage events & opportunities (D11.3):

- **Research centres and academic institutes**, such as INILAB* and PNO Innovation*, represent a key segment, using the instrument for scientific studies related to marine radioactivity, geohazards, and environmental monitoring;
- **Geology and Resource Exploration Industry**, particularly organisations involved in the characterisation of natural resources for exploitation, like oil, rare earth elements, and uranium on or beneath the seabed;

- **Civil protection authorities and regulatory agencies** in the environmental, atmospheric, and oceanic domains that can use the technology to monitor radiological hazards and ensure compliance with safety standards;
- **Enterprises that develop and commercialise autonomous platforms** such as landers, marine drones, and AUVs, can integrate the spectrometer in these platforms;
- **Previous customers** who have used earlier versions of the technology for shallow water applications, now seeking to extend capabilities to greater depths.

Channels

The deep ocean radioactivity sensor reaches its target audiences through a **diverse range of key channels**. Online channels include the **websites of NAUTILOS, HCMR, and HORST**, which serve as central sources of information. For now, promotional materials include **NAUTILOS leaflet**, that can be used to clearly communicate the key features and benefits of this technology to a broad audience. **Word-of-mouth from previous customers** plays a significant role in expanding awareness and credibility. The publication of **peer-reviewed scientific papers** helps showcase the instrument's performance and achievements in research contexts. Outreach is further strengthened through **personalised direct contacts** (e.g., email, phone calls, messaging, and meetings). Finally, visibility is maximised through active **participation in specialised exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows**. In this sense, throughout the NAUTILOS project, the deep ocean radioactivity sensor ensured the presence in several events such as the International Shenzhen Global Innovation Forum of Talents 2024 (invitation only).

Customer relationships

Customer relationships are built on **dedicated personal assistance**, particularly during the initial installation and first deployment of the spectrometer, ensuring smooth onboarding and successful integration into operational workflows. In the event of technical issues, customers benefit from **prompt and reliable technical support**. Collaboration is further strengthened through a **win-win consortium approach**, where mutual value is created by aligning the objectives of developers and customers/users. This fosters trust, long-term engagement, and shared success in scientific and commercial applications.

Revenue Streams

The deep ocean radioactivity sensor is available at a **fixed price**, however there is a room for discount negotiation where commercially appropriate. There are various ways to possibly generate revenue from each customer segment, including: **direct sales to customers; leasing; additional fees**, depending on customer needs, which include services such as **extra technical support, data analysis, and product customisation**. Regarding the payment type, a **variable billing system** (pre or post-payment) can be considered depending on the customer's needs. In projects involving both public and private entities, **co-financing models** are often considered to facilitate collaboration and shared investment.

Key Resources

The business relies on essential physical resources, such as **raw materials, component parts, scientific payloads**, and dedicated **production facilities** to manufacture the instruments. Human resources encompass skilled **engineering, operational, and sales teams**, who are responsible for product development, manufacturing, and market engagement respectively.

Furthermore, expertise in **intellectual property management and contract negotiation** is crucial for protecting innovations and fostering commercial partnerships.

Key Activities

Core activities include the **manufacturing and assembling of instruments**, ensuring quality and reliability throughout production. Also, **customisation services** are offered to tailor products to specific customer requirements. **Sales efforts** focus on market outreach and customer acquisition. **Technical support** is provided both remotely and on-site as needed, to assist customers with installation, problem solving, and maintenance. Additional activities **site characterisation** and **data analysis capabilities** (from post-processing of collected data to near real-time analysis, depending on customer needs) are considered key for a successful and profitable business.

<p>Key Partnership</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw materials, parts, payload suppliers (e.g. crystal supplier for the sensor construction) Partners to perform testing and demonstration (e.g. pressure testing in hyperbaric chamber) Consortia (EU and international) for the assessment of radioactivity levels Collaborative partnerships with companies and other relevant institutions interested in the assessment of radioactivity levels (check 'Customer Segments' box) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturing and assembling Sales Technical support provision (remote or on-site if needed) Customization based on customer needs Data analysis (from post processing to near real time, based on client need) Site characterization <p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical (raw materials, parts, payload, production facilities) Human (engineering, operational and sales teams) Expertise in IP management and contracts 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost-effective Underwater in-situ gamma-ray spectrometer for deep ocean monitoring (up to 3000 m) Tool for increasing surveillance (reducing data gaps) of radioactivity levels by monitoring radioactive substances through advanced analysis methods in the context of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> anthropogenic hazards (dangerous nuclear materials in the ocean) or natural hazards (due to earthquakes and volcanic activity in submarine faults) Exploiting natural mining resources (by detection radon gas or any other related material from the earth crust) Smart service (raw data, analysed results, site characterization according to contamination level) Reliable, easy to use and adaptable to different applications and installations methods Enables radioactivity profiling along with depth and correlation with CTD data to identify water masses Long-lasting deployment* (25 days of continuous operation) <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 demonstration activities in the North Sea, Cretan Sea and Ionian Sea</p>	<p>Customer relationship</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicated personal assistance, including during first try installation Prompt technical support in case of a problem Win-win consortium <p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website (NAUTILOS, HCMR and HORST) NAUTILOS Sensor Leaflet NAUTILOS newsletter Word-of-mouth from previous customers Scientific papers to showcase achievements Personalized direct contacts (e.g. email, telephone, instant messaging, meetings) Specialized exhibitions, Conferences and Trade Shows (e.g. EMD 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*, International Shenzhen Global Innovation Forum of Talents 2024*) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research Centers and academic institutes (e.g. INILAB*, PNO Innovation Portugal*) Industry (Geology) that perform characterisation of natural resources for exploitation (oil, rare earth, uranium) Civil protection and regulatory bodies (Environment/atmospheric/oceanic authorities/agencies) Enterprises that commercialize autonomous units (lander, marine drones, AUVs etc) Previous customers of using the sensor/system for shallow waters <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p> <p>Fixed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human resources (engineering, operational and sales teams) Infrastructures (office, laboratories) Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and up to 2-year guarantee) Intellectual Property and Legal (contracts, patent) <p>Variable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquisition of raw materials, parts and payload (e.g. critical expenses include the crystal module) Expenses with testing and demonstration Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) Extra technical support (if requested by the customer, e.g. first try installation for long term operation) Site characterization and data analysis (if requested by the customer) Product customization (if requested by the customer) Royalties (if applicable) 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <p>Pricing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed Discount or negotiation where commercially appropriate <p>Type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product sales Leasing Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extra technical support Data analysis Product customization <p>Payment type</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) Co-financing is commonly considered (when we have a public and private entity) 		

Figure 47: Business Model Canvas for the deep ocean radioactivity sensor, designed by Christos Tsabaris (HCMR), Marios Anagnostou (HORST Ltd) and WP11 Team.

Key partnerships

Key partnerships include **key suppliers** of raw materials, components, and payloads, in particular **specialised crystal suppliers** essential for sensor construction. Dedicated partners to perform critical **testing and demonstration** including **pressure testing in hyperbaric chambers**, are critical to ensure instrument reliability under deep-sea conditions. The active participation in **consortia at both EU and international levels** focused on the assessment of radioactivity levels, fostering knowledge exchange and joint development, is considered essential for business development. Additional strategic collaborations with **companies and institutions aligned with radioactivity monitoring objectives** (as outlined in the Customer Segments) further strengthen product capabilities and market reach.

Cost structure

The main costs involved in manufacturing the deep ocean radioactivity sensor are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include **human resources** such as engineering, operational, and sales teams, **infrastructure expenses** covering offices and laboratories, **basic technical support** provided within pre-established hours and including up to a two-year product guarantee, and **intellectual property management and legal costs** related to contracts and patents. **Variable costs** include the **acquisition of raw materials, parts, and payloads**, with critical expenses including components like the **crystal module**. Additional variable expenses arise from **testing and demonstration activities**, **marketing** expenses such as participation in exhibitions, and **extra technical support** if requested by the customer, including first try installation for long-term operations. **Site characterisation, data analysis, and product customisation services**, when requested by customers, also contribute to variable costs. **Royalties** may apply depending on the future licensing agreement.

In continuity with the preceding BMC analysis, the following Table 12 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 12: Deep ocean radioactivity sensor (HCMR) Exploitation ID card.

DEEP OCEAN RADIOACTIVITY SENSOR (HCMR) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 1 developed prototype, available for HCMR for further testing <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.4)</small>
	Applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership HCMR
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by HORST Ltd (joint initiatives ongoing & licensing agreement under discussion with HCMR) <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis Improved Technology and Cheaper in Class <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis One single competitor <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

XIII. SRDL-CTD-OXY ANIMAL TAG (CNRS/SMRU)

The **SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal-borne instrument** (Figure 48) results from the addition of a sensor measuring **dissolved oxygen** in the Argos CTD-SRDL (conductivity-temperature-depth satellite relayed data logger) tags from the **Sea Mammal Research Unit (SMRU)**. It was developed in the scope of the NAUTILOS project, to allow for the monitoring of dissolved oxygen and correlation with other oceanographic parameters, as no other non-invasive tagging solution available worldwide (D11.5). This compact, lightweight animal tag is the **first commercially available, long-term deployment device for measuring dissolved oxygen** in marine environments designed for use on large air-breathing animals such as seals and turtles. Designed for **deployments of up to 5 months**, this marine animal-borne satellite tag provides critical **behavioral and oceanographic data from depths of up to 2,000 meters**, including high-resolution measurements of pressure, temperature, and conductivity. The system transmits low-resolution real-time data twice a day, with the possibility to download high resolution data after recovering the device. Being an essential tool for obtaining data in remote and **hard-to-access regions** (cold, temperate, and tropical waters), the tag leverages proven CTD technology that has demonstrated reliable performance for over two decades, particularly in the Southern Hemisphere.

Marine animal-borne temperature-salinity-DO tag

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000925 (NAUTILOS).

www.smru.st-andrews.ac.uk/instrumentation
www.cebc.cnrs.fr/infrastructures/bio-logging

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 NAUTILOS

A marine animal-borne (seals and turtles) satellite tag for measuring and transmitting behavioral and oceanic data.

Measurable parameters	dissolved oxygen NEW conductivity pressure temperature
Conductivity range	0 to 0.08 S/cm (± 0.001)
Dissolved oxygen range	0 to 16 mg/L (± 0.002)
Temperature range	-5 to 35 °C (± 0.005)
Data transmission	satellite (Argos) - 4 profiles per day; up to 50 000 full length Argos data transmissions
Data archival	SD card, logged internally (P/T/Y/O : 0.5 Hz; acceleration : 12 Hz)
Depth rating	2 000 m
Mission duration	5 months (continuous)
Power	lithium battery
Dimensions (L x W x H)	105 x 80 x 80 mm
Weight (air)	545 g
Weight (water)	250 g

Figure 48: SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag (CNRS/SMRU) leaflet.

As reported in D7.6, SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag fulfilled all expected **10 deployments** (Figure 49), and provided a significant number of datasets for the Southern Ocean, proving to be an **essential tool for marine researchers** seeking to expand observational coverage in ocean regions where quality data is scarce by taking advantage of the natural movement patterns of marine predators. Out of the 10 tags deployed, 9 were recovered and 3 units developed will remain available for CNRS-CEBC deployments for future. Considering **operational capability and reliability** proved through CNRS-CEBC deployments, SMRU targets to start **SRDL-CTD-Oxy early sales** with key partnerships for the **next summer/fall (May/June 2026)**.

Figure 49: Evidence from WP7 NAUTILOS demonstration activities conducted using the SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag, in an operational environment – Southern Ocean (more information in D7.6): SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tags on an elephant seal (left); datasets made available through the NAUTILOS data portal on the project website (right).

The SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tags was classified as **“New to Market”** (D11.5) under the competitor and market analysis that was conducted. It is the first long-term deployment seal tag for the study of dissolved oxygen to be readily available for purchase, therefore there is no equivalent or comparable competitor on the market.

The following sections will present all the other components (apart from the value proposition presented above) of the Business Model Canvas for the specific sensor under discussion, covering all standard elements: **Customer Segments, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partnerships, and Cost Structure**. The final BMC, designed by Christophe Guinet (CNRS-CEBC) and the WP11 Team, and subsequently validated by SMRU, is presented on Figure 51.

Customer segments

The marine animal-borne satellite tag is designed to serve a range of customers involved in marine research, conservation, and monitoring. Key customers include:

- **Universities and research centers**, particularly those focused on marine ecology (e.g., Centre d’Études Biologiques de Chizé (CNRS-CEBC) and PNO Innovation, which was identified as potential customer in NAUTILOS brokerage events, D11.3);
- **Local, national, and supranational authorities** responsible for ocean monitoring represent another important customer group, using the tag to support policy-making, environmental assessments, and compliance with marine protection regulations;
- **Marine conservation foundations and national parks**, which rely on robust, long-term data to inform conservation strategies, habitat protection, and ecosystem management efforts in coastal and open-ocean environments.

Channels

The SRDL-CTD-Oxy reaches its target audience through a **variety of channels**, mainly including digital platforms, direct outreach and industry events. Key online sources include the **NAUTILOS, CNRS, and SMRU websites**, which provide visibility and access to detailed information about the technology. Promotional materials such as the **NAUTILOS leaflet**, developed specifically under WP11, can be used to clearly communicate the key features and benefits of this technology to a broad audience. Customer engagement is further strengthened through personalised direct contacts (e.g. email, phone calls, instant messaging, meetings), ensuring tailored support. **Word-of-mouth plays a significant role** in expanding awareness, as also the participation at specialised exhibitions, conferences, and trade shows. During NAUTILOS, the tag marked presence at EMD 2024 and Sea Tech Week 2024 (Figure 50), as many other relevant events as the 36th annual European Cetacean Society Conference held in Ponta Delgada (São Miguel Island, Azores, Portugal), from 12 to 16th of May 2025.

Figure 50: SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag (CNRS/SMRU) showcased at SEA TECH WEEK 2024. Catarina Lemos (CEiIA) and Christophe Guinet (CNRS-CEBC) at NAUTILOS Booth, with NAUTILOS merchandising and leaflets booklet.

Customer relationships

When it comes to building and maintaining relationships with each customer segment, **dedicated personal assistance** that focuses strongly on responsiveness and individual customer needs is essential. This customer-oriented approach ensures users receive expert guidance and support throughout the product lifecycle. **Prompt technical support** is available both **remotely and on-site (if possible)** in the event of issues or setup requirements, helping to maintain system performance and customer satisfaction.

Revenue Streams

There are different ways to possibly earn revenue with this value proposition, whether it is through direct product sales or additional fees, depending on customer needs, such as extra/long-term technical support, or data analysis and post-processing of data. In terms of how the customer can pay for the products, a variable billing system (pre or post-payment) can be considered.

Key Resources

The resources that are essential for the production of the marine animal-borne satellite tag include essential **raw materials and payload** required for the production of the tag. The product is developed and assembled in dedicated **manufacturing facilities**, supported by **quality testing laboratories** and **demonstration infrastructure** to ensure reliability and performance under real-world conditions. The development process is driven by a skilled **engineering team** for mechanical and electronic development, while a **data science team** supports the processing and delivery of collected data. In addition, **sales teams** play a crucial role in customer engagement, market development, and ongoing commercial support.

Key Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities and research centers (e.g. Centre d'Études Biologiques de Chizé (CEBC_CNRS)) Specialized sensor suppliers for tag (e.g., dissolved oxygen sensor) Partners to perform testing and demonstration (e.g., relevant offshore testing, pressure housing testing) 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design and manufacturing Calibration and validation Technical support provision Marketing & Sales Continuous R&D to stay competitive and improve the product Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw materials, payload Manufacturing facilities Quality testing laboratories and demonstration facilities Engineering team for mechanical and electronic development Data science team Sales teams 	Value Propositions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A marine animal-borne (seals and turtles) satellite tag for measuring and transmitting behavioral and oceanic data up to 2000m First commercially available long-term deployment tag for measuring dissolved oxygen, designed for use on a wide range of large air-breathing predators Additional high-resolution data acquisition of pressure, temperature and conductivity Mission duration of up to 5 months (continuous) Low resolution real-time data (twice a day) with possibility to download high resolution data after recovering the device Compact and lightweight An essential tool for obtaining data mostly from remote oceans and coastal areas, including cold, temperate, and tropical waters, based on a proved CTD technology working efficiently in the southern hemisphere for over 20 years <p>*NAUTILOS WP7 deployments on Southern elephant seals in the Antarctic/Southern Ocean</p>	Customer relationship <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dedicated personal assistance, highly customer focused Prompt technical support, available both remotely and on-site (if possible) Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website (NAUTILOS, CNRS, SMRU) Leaflet (NAUTILOS) NAUTILOS newsletter Personalised direct contacts (e.g. email, telephone, instant messaging, meetings) Word-of-mouth Specialized exhibitions, Conferences and Trade Shows (e.g., EMD 2024*, Sea Tech Week 2024*, European Cetacean Society Conference 2025*) <p>*NAUTILOS Brokerage Events & Opportunities</p>	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Universities and Research Centers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Marine Ecology researchers (e.g. Centre d'Études Biologiques de Chizé (CEBC_CNRS), PNO Innovation Portugal*) Local, national and supranational authorities for ocean monitoring Marine conservation foundations National Parks <p>*Potential customers identified in NAUTILOS Brokerage Events</p>
Cost Structure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human resources (engineering, data science and sales team) Manufacturing infrastructures Basic technical support (pre-established HR hours and guarantee) Variable <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw materials, payload acquisition and production costs Calibration and validation Technical support (extra support) Shipping and logistics Marketing expenses (e.g. exhibitions) 		Revenue Streams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fixed pricing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Product sales Additional fees (depending on customer needs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extra technical support Data analysis and post-processing Payment type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variable billing system (pre or post-payment) 		

Figure 51: Business Model Canvas for the SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag, designed by Christophe Guinet (CNRS-CEBC) and the WP11 Team, and subsequently validated by SMRU.

Key Activities

Core activities include the **design and manufacturing** of the satellite tag, ensuring high performance, durability, and suitability for long-term deployment on marine animals. **Calibration and validation** processes are critical to guarantee data accuracy and reliability under varying environmental conditions. **Technical support provision** is also a key activity, both during installation and throughout the product's operational life. **Marketing and sales** efforts focus on promoting the product across relevant customer segments. In parallel, **continuous research and development (R&D)** ensures the product remains competitive, incorporating technological advancements and responding to emerging user needs.

Key partnerships

Key partnerships include **universities and research centers**, such as the **Centre d'Études Biologiques de Chizé (CNRS-CEBC)**, which contribute to product validation, field testing, and scientific collaboration. **Specialised sensor suppliers** to incorporate in the tags, particularly for components like the **dissolved oxygen sensor**, are essential for ensuring high-quality, reliable measurement capabilities. In addition, collaboration with **testing and demonstration**

partners - including facilities capable of **offshore deployment trials** and **pressure housing testing** - is critical for verifying performance under realistic environmental conditions.

Cost structure

The main costs involved in manufacturing this product are divided into fixed and variable costs. **Fixed costs** include **human resources** such as engineering, data science, and sales teams, infrastructure expenses, and **basic technical support** provided within pre-established hours and including product guarantee. **Variable costs** include the **acquisition of raw materials, payload, and production expenses**. Additional variable expenses arise from **extra technical support** if requested by the customer, **marketing** expenses such as participation in exhibitions, and **shipping and logistics**.

In continuity with the preceding BMC analysis, the following Table 13 offers a structured synthesis of complementary dimensions relevant to the NAUTILOS "Road to Market" process, including benchmarking against competitors, preliminary merchandising approaches, projections concerning the deployment and utilisation of future units and early sales.

Table 13: SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag (CNRS/SMRU) Exploitation ID card.

SRDL-CTD-OXY ANIMAL TAG (CNRS/SMRU) Exploitation ID card	
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT	Future use of NAUTILOS units 3 developed units will remain available for CNRS-CEBC deployments for future <small>(for more information about WP7 demonstrations and final TRL, please check D7.6)</small>
	Not applicable for freshwater applications
	IPR Ownership SMRU
	IPR Protection Without formal IP protection, relying instead on trade secrets
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	Commercialisation strategy To be commercialized by SMRU <small>(for more information, please check specific BMC above)</small>
	Merchandising Material YES (from NAUTILOS); presented in NAUTILOS brokerage events <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.3)</small>
	Cost-Benefit Analysis New to Market <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>
	Competitor's analysis No direct competitors <small>(for more information, please check specific D11.5)</small>

XIV. SCALING-UP, REPLICATION AND TRANSFERABILITY OF THE NAUTILOS SOLUTIONS

This chapter relates activities developed in “Task 11.2 Instrumentation Roadmap. Scalability, replicability and transferability study”. It describes major efforts made to ensure scalability of NAUTILOS KERs relying on all expected actions from NAUTILOS GA and other additional opportunities.

Actions expected from NAUTILOS GA related with:

- **NIVA was expected to exploit microplastic sampling and analytical devices (sensors) for freshwater and drinking water applications**, in particular related with NIVA/CSEM instrument under development in NAUTILOS. Unfortunately, NIVA did not pursue the fresh or drinking water application because the new drinking water directive for microplastics does not allow other methods than uFTIR or uRAMAN (NIVA/CSEM uses fluorescence dye not supported on new requirements in EUs drinking water directive). This being said, in WP11, exploitation for freshwater focused on evaluating how many NAUTILOS sensors were suitable for freshwater. This information was provided for all NAUTILOS KERs on their individual Exploitation ID card;
- **DFKI was expected to contribute to fostering the transferability of the solution linkages with the World Bank’s**. Given their focus on river pollution, - all NAUTILOS KER sensors applicable to freshwater - along with those related to plastic pollution - were specifically highlighted. This action was developed and is currently ongoing, reported in detail later on this D11.7.

Additional activities:

- Individual interactions, ongoing or to be started based on the specific interest from stakeholders shared during NAUTILOS brokerage events (reported on previous individual sections for each NAUTILOS KER);
- LANDSEALOT project (reported below);
- BOOSTER initiative (reported below);
- SCOOP catalogue - All NAUTILOS leaflets were shared to be included in the SCOOP catalogue.

LANDSEALOT PROJECT

LandSeaLot is a Horizon Europe project that seeks to integrate and enhance existing coastal observation efforts including in situ, satellite, modelling and citizen science to better study the land-sea interface area, where terrestrial and marine habitats meet.

LandSeaLot includes the acquisition of low-cost technologies (Figure 52). **All opportunities have been shared with the NAUTILOS consortium**. Initially, in 2024, during a TIB meeting, Antonio Novellino, a common partner from NAUTILOS and LandSeaLot, presented the project, and **advertised the procurement process from ETT**.

Considering that LandSeaLot calls need “ready to market” (meaning TRL9) sensors for specific EOVs, during one-to-one meetings, partners discussed with the TIM the possibility to register NAUTILOS commercial products. It was concluded that **NKE was the only partner offering instruments suitable for acquisition** within the scope of this project, **having registered in time for ETT’s procurement survey and submitted a commercial quotation.**

Figure 52: Antonio Novellino presenting the LandSeaLot project during a NAUTILOS technology and innovation board meeting.

All recent funding calls have also been shared with partners, and the project received renewed visibility during the NAUTILOS final event.

WORLD BANK GROUP

The World Bank is like a cooperative, made up of 189 member countries. These member countries, or shareholders, are represented by a Board of Governors, who are the ultimate policymakers at the World Bank. The World Bank is the collective name for the International Bank for Reconstruction, Development (IBRD), International Development Association (IDA), International Finance Corporation (IFC), Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA), and the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID). As originally the World Bank was meant to finance the reconstruction after World War two it is nowadays an international financial institution that provides loans and grants to the governments of low- and middle-income countries for the purposes of economic development.

World Bank supports a large variety of projects, among different locations. An updated map (<https://maps.worldbank.org/projects>) shows the number of projects per country (Figure 53).

Figure 53: World Bank map showing supported projects around the World (<https://maps.worldbank.org/projects>).

Data and analysis have shown that the majority of plastic waste that reaches the ocean comes from rivers. As 8 out of the 10 most ocean-polluting rivers were located in Asia, the World Bank identified the need for mitigation measures. The World Bank initiated a project for the development of a smart detection system to evaluate the amount and type of plastic that passes rivers. As a cooperation project with DFKI and local administrative departments for environmental protection three projects were conducted. The first project was focusing on the rivers Siem Reap and Sihanoukville in Cambodia, the second project should assist the governments of Cambodia and Myanmar to develop and implement plastic action plans to reduce the amount of plastic waste entering the environment. Finally, the third project focuses on implementing long term observations also on the Philippines as one of the most polluted bay areas of the world is located in this region.

These projects were done with a World Bank representative for South and East Asia. Considering World Bank engagement as part of the exploitation strategy, **NAUTILOS results were shared to lead attention of the World Bank to this new state of the art results.** This information could be used by the World Bank to consult World Bank related activities in these regions for **increase of water quality and reduction of waste contamination**, as also to **enhance funding opportunities and expand access to broader networks for disseminating NAUTILOS results.**

The World Bank contact was invited to the NAUTILOS final event. Despite the interest it was not possible to attend, however **DFKI pointed to the publicly available video of the NAUTILOS final event as well as to the results page showing the different instrumentation developed** within NAUTILOS, along with specific leaflets for NAUTILOS sensors that especially could be used in the freshwater scenario or could easily be adapted to it. Also, it was offered the World Bank the **possibility to establish contact with any of the NAUTILOS partners** (especially the sensor developers) in case of interest, and also **shared the interest from SubCTech to replicate NAUTILOS demonstration activities with the submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics, if considered, in the scope of South and East Asia World Bank activities.**

BOOSTER INITIATIVE

Maximising the impact of EU-funded research is among the key objectives of the EU’s investment in research and innovation, as too many discoveries and innovations remain on the shelf after the end of a project. To help bridge the gap between the achievement of results and their impact on the ground, the Booster initiative set out to increase the dissemination and exploitation of research and innovation results through several different free-of-charge services.

Booster is a collaborative & support-driven learning experience, for all market domains, that provide free guidance for EU-funded research results. It includes two core services: dissemination support and go-to-market services (Figure 54). It is a non-competitive application and continuously open, with a structured approach that focuses also on adapting to each project KER. **The BOOSTER process for the NAUTILOS project started in January 2025** (Figure 55). After an initial meeting (04/02/2025) to better understand the process, the **application was submitted on 06/05/2025**.

Figure 54: Core services from BOOSTER presented during the Booster Info session (18/06/2025).

Beneficiary organisation				
Organisation name	Organisation PIC	Project	Contact person	Contact person's email
CEIIA - CENTRO DE ENGENHARIA E DESENVOLVIMENTO (ASSOCIACAO)	973080139	NAUTILOS	Catarina Lemos	catarina.lemos@ceiiia.com

 This application has been submitted on 06/05/2025 and is currently under evaluation. You will be notified by e-mail about the results of the evaluation as soon as possible

Figure 55: NAUTILOS registration for BOOSTER services.

After approval, experts for the entry level consultation were assigned. Since then, three actions took place to organize and structure NAUTILOS BOOSTER journey:

- Online workshop / Conference call - Date: 26/05/2025 | 1st Meeting with the Beneficiary;
- Online workshop / Conference call - Date: 05/06/2025 | 2nd Meeting with the Beneficiary - The service roadmap was agreed upon;
- Online session - Date: 18/06/2025 | Booster Info session - Booster Info Session: free guidance for EU-funded research result.

NAUTILOS BOOSTER application will be a multi-partner process with 3 KER. All KER results were contacted for the BOOSTER opportunity, after the first meeting with the entry level consultation experts. **TOP 3 KER for NAUTILOS was decided based on their need for additional exploitation support for the future go-to-market strategy and partners availability,** and include 3 NAUTILOS partners (with the non-permanent presence of other relevant early adopters or commercial partners, as needed):

- **CEiia - MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag** | A non-invasive towed marine animal (sharks and mantas) tagging platform for measuring behavioral and oceanic data (Figure 56);
- **AQUATEC - AQUAscet Mk2** | A high-frequency profiling sensor for sediment studies and marine biology (Figure 56);
- **HCMR - Deep ocean radioactivity sensor** | Underwater in-situ gamma-ray spectrometer for the deep ocean (Figure 56).

Figure 56: Leaflets from the three NAUTILOS KER to be involved in BOOSTER.

All the other “non-involved KER” either already have early sales or will continue the remaining development and go-to-market approach independently.

The agreed BOOSTER service roadmap timeline is available on Table 14. **It is important to highlight NAUTILOS partners commitment after the end of the project (30/06/2025), since the action plan will start in October 2025.** Following the conclusion of the currently expected services, additional services such as networking may be added upon request.

Table 14: BOOSTER service roadmap timeline for NAUTILOS KER selected.

BOOSTER SERVICES	TIMELINE
2.3 G2M - Module A: Kick-off	October 2025
2.3 G2M - Module B: Key exploitable results (KERs) & Unique Value Proposition (UVP)	October 2025
2.3 G2M - Module D: Business Plan	November 2025
2.3 G2M - Module E: Access to other funding & entrepreneurship support	December 2025/ January 2026
3.5 Audio Visual Support	November 2025

During BOOSTER services, NAUTILOS KERS are expected to have support on how to channel products and teams to continue development from the final TRL stages in NAUTILOS up to

TRL 9 and achieve effective market sales. Among others, this opportunity will give teams the opportunity to:

- discuss the unique value proposition, pre-defined in WP11, with BOOSTER experts;
- validate or improve their business plan and exploitation strategy, pre-defined in WP11, with BOOSTER experts;
- Discuss future opportunities to continue and increase the impact already achieved in the scope of NAUTILOS, mainly through the “Module E - Access to other funding”. Access to funding is considered a priority, for example via EIC Accelerator, a funding programme under Horizon Europe that offers support to start-ups and SMEs that have an innovative, game changing product, service or business model that could create new markets or disrupt existing ones in Europe and even worldwide.

XV. OPEN ACCESS INSTRUMENTATION ROADMAP (OJAR)

This section presents the **final OJAR developments**: the final **database** and the first **Microsoft Power BI prototype** of the Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap.

As previously stated, challenges associated with ocean monitoring lie not only in the availability of instrumentation for effective data collection, mainly to monitor specific EOVs, but also in the sharing of these monitoring solutions among various stakeholders. The increasing complexity of technologies in the field of ocean observation has highlighted the need for decision-support tools that integrate scattered technical data in an accessible, clear, and interactive manner. Also, in the domain of ocean monitoring instrumentation information is often fragmented across various entities, hindering its strategic use by researchers, companies, or policymakers. The NAUTILOS project, in the scope of WP11, tackles this market gap: the lack of a database concept that centralizes information on existing instruments and their technical specifications to facilitate access to ocean monitoring instrumentation.

Initial methodology was presented in Deliverable D11.2 Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap.

OJAR - METHODOLOGY

D11.2 outlines NAUTILOS proposal for OJAR database development with a multi-step data collection methodology so that a set of reliable and updated marine instrumentation data is collected and shared. NAUTILOS OJAR multi-step data collection methodology included the following actions:

- **Online data collection** was primarily conducted through official websites and online catalogues of instrument developers, as well as event pages (e.g., exhibitions and demo days). **Attempts to use AI Tools to structure information proved ineffective**, as the tool did not compile sufficiently specific information for the intended technical requirements;
- Through a **questionnaire** developed in the scope of WP11 (shared in D11.2) and sent to stakeholders by e-mail, to over 250 contacts including NAUTILOS partners and other projects (eg. TechOceanS), but also shared in NAUTILOS and NAUTILOS partners social media networks (Figure 57);
- **Direct interaction with relevant stakeholders** taking place during NAUTILOS brokerage events and other outreach opportunities, as detailed in D11.3. During these events, brochures (Figure 58) specifically designed by WP10 for the NAUTILOS Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap (OJAR) were distributed (Figure 59). Additionally, participating entities were invited to complete the form directly on a tablet, a method that proved to be highly effective and well received.

Figure 57: NAUTILOS OAIR direct survey shared on social media networks.

Figure 58: NAUTILOS OAIR brochure developed to be distributed during NAUTILOS brokerage events and other opportunities.

Figure 59: NAUTILOS OIAR brochures displayed during brokerage events (left and middle). Participants completing the OAIR questionnaire directly on a tablet with support from a NAUTILOS representative (left).

Despite the low engagement observed during the AtlantOS project - where only 12 out of 136 contacted entities replied – OIAR team decided to make a **new attempt to collect data through a questionnaire considering that the required information is difficult to locate online or requires validation**. Unfortunately, and despite the **additional effort on sharing and promoting**, the **engagement was again reduced**, and thus most of our data was collected from online sources (official websites). Recognizing the critical importance of validation from developers, the OAIR team decided to **implement an additional activity in collaboration with NAUTILOS partners (AQUATEC, SubCTech, and NKE)**, requesting data validation. This approach proved to be **highly effective**, as partners reported it to be easier, less demanding, and more practical than providing exhaustive listings from scratch. **Validation activities carried out with NAUTILOS partners demonstrated the high quality of the data compiled by the OAIR team, however confirming that validation is still considered as an essential step before making OAIR publicly available.**

OIAR - DATABASE

NAUTILOS produced two separate databases. The first one “**Entities and Exhibitions**” table refers to the list of organisations operating in the ocean monitoring market and compiles comprehensive data about entities, mostly from the market point of view. **Final data compilation includes 313 entities, from over 30 countries**, representing a 130% increase compared to the initial AtlantOS dataset (136 entities). “Entities and Exhibitions Table” attributes (Figure 60) include the following:

- Organisation name
- Country
- Entity type (Industry, Research, HEI and Other)
- Does it sell sensors?
- Does it have an online catalogue?
- Is it present in exhibitions/demo days?

Organization	Country	Entity Type	Does it sell sensors?	Does it have an online catalog?	Is it present in exhibitions/demo days?
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	Germany	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS	Norway	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
AARHUS UNIVERSITET	Denmark	HEI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Abyssens	France	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ACRI-ST	France	Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AEL Aberdeen Ltd	UK	Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC)	Spain	Research	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Airmar Technology	USA	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Albatross marine tech	Spain	Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Alpha Controls	Canada	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AML Oceanographic	Canada	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
AMT GmbH	Germany	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ANB Sensors	UK	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Antwerp maritime academy	Belgium	Research	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Aquaread	UK	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Aquatec	UK	Industry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Arctic Rays Subsea Technologies	USA	Industry	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 60: OIAR “Entities and Exhibitions” table - data collected online without partner validation, based on publicly available sources such as official websites.

The second table, entitled “Instrumentation” table consolidates, in a single location, names and technical specifications of commercial instruments currently available for ocean monitoring. It was created following the NAUTILOS OIAR questionnaire (D11.2). However, based on information gathered from online sources and questionnaire responses, the final structure of the table was simplified. “Instrumentation Table” attributes include the following:

- GENERAL INFORMATION
 - Organisation
 - Country
 - Organisation's website
 - Instrument
 - Please provide a brief description of the sensor or instrument (optional)
 - Type of instrument
 - Instrument website
- TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS
 - Depth of operation [m]
 - Standalone?
 - Data connection needed?
 - Power connection needed?
 - Range (per variable)
 - Accuracy (per variable)
 - Resolution (per variable)
 - Unit (per variable)
 - Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)
 - 01. Physics
 - 02. Biochemistry
 - 03. Biology and Ecosystems
 - 04. Cross-disciplinary (including human impact)
 - 05. Other variables covered
 - Suitable for operation in freshwater/saltwater/both
 - Platforms that can be integrated (optional)
 - Application/commercial purpose (optional)

When compared to the AtlantOS reference database, apart from the significant increase of data compiled, there's another major difference: the focus on commercial instrumentation (mainly TRL9). While AtlantOS focus on project results despite their current technology readiness, OIAR focus on fostering ocean monitoring by making mature instrumentation easily available (despite the project involved). **This was a strategic decision based on feedback collected (from both AtlantOS and NAUTILOS activities).** Nevertheless, initially the attribute "Projects associated with sensor development" was considered however due to the lack of information it was removed. Also, there were very few references to topics such as "Calibration or maintenance," or "Use of reagents or chemicals.". Even when sensor developers were contacted directly, this type of specific information appears to be typically shared only through direct contact, and for this reason it was deleted.

A **comprehensive OIAR instrumentation catalogue is provided in Appendix 3**, detailing information collected to support the development of the OIAR database: institution name, institution website and instrument designation. **Final data compilation includes 390 instruments**, representing a 572% increase compared to the initial AtlantOS dataset (58 instruments).

OIAR - MICROSOFT POWER BI PROTOTYPE

Raw data, whether in tables or text, **does not allow for the identification of patterns, trends, or relationships** (Sahaya et al., 2024). This is why **data visualisation** becomes a powerful **tool for drawing conclusions** about a specific issue (Al-Sulaiti et al., 2021).

Within this context, and as part of the present project NAUTILOS, the first prototype of an interactive digital platform was developed using Microsoft Power BI, a software that truly helps transform simple data into smarter business decisions. The platform was designed to consolidate and explore technical information from the comprehensive OAIR database. The process included the construction of dashboards geared toward the geographic, technical, and functional analysis of the identified instruments. **This approach enables researchers, policymakers, funders, and companies interested in marine technology to access relevant information quickly and intuitively.**

In order to achieve this, CEiiA made an extra effort (not expected in the scope of the present grant agreement) within the framework of an academic thesis at the University of Aveiro (Industrial Engineering and Management), aiming to develop the first Microsoft Power BI prototype of the OIAR, under the NAUTILOS project, as in the scope of D11.2.

The methodology involved data transformation, relational modelling, and the creation of advanced filtering mechanisms, resulting in a solution tailored to the complexity and diversity of the collected information.

OIAR database normalisation for Microsoft Power BI

The data structuring and normalisation phase was primarily driven by the need to convert the collected information into a format compatible with Microsoft Power BI. At the same time,

this step allowed for the identification and correction of inconsistencies, as well as the validation of previously entered data, ensuring greater accuracy and consistency.

Due to the complex nature of the table and the granularity of the collected data, one proposed solution was to **reorganize the “Instrumentation Table” table into two complementary tables (“General Characteristics” and “Sensor and Type”)** to ensure the representation of distinct technical specifications for the same instrument and enable faster and more efficient data updates (Figure 61). Separating this information from the rest helps avoid redundancy and the repetition of identical data across rows referring to the same instrument but associated with different EOVs. All tables underwent a **process of duplicate instance removal and standardisation of common values** to enable proper linkage in the conceptual and relational model within Microsoft Power BI.

Organization	Instrument	Type of sensor	Min Range	Max Range	Accuracy	Resolution	Unit
Proteus Instruments	Proteus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter	Nitrate	0	100	±5% or 2	0.01	mg/l
Proteus Instruments	Proteus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter	Chloride	0	18000	±5% or 2	0.01	mg/l
Proteus Instruments	Proteus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter	Sodium	0	20000	±5% or 2	0.01	mg/l
Proteus Instruments	Proteus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter	Calcium	0	40000	±5% or 2	0.01	mg/l
Proteus Instruments	Proteus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter	Bromide	0	80000	±5% or 2	0.01	mg/l
Proteus Instruments	Proteus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter	Total dissolved gas	600	800	±0.1	0.1	mmHg

Figure 61: OIAR “Sensor and Type” Table – sample of data collected online without partner validation, based on publicly available sources such as official websites.

After normalizing the tables to ensure they contained the necessary and appropriate attributes, primary and foreign keys were defined for each table to establish relationships between entities, as illustrated in Figure 62. Relationships in a relational model can be one-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-many; however, in this project's model, only one-to-many relationships are present. For example, each entity can own one or multiple instruments, but each instrument belongs to only one entity. Regarding sensor specifications, a sensor can have several technical specifications, depending on the number of variables (EOVs) it is capable of measuring. However, each specification is exclusively linked to the sensor it describes, further reinforcing the one-to-many relational model.

Afterwards, the database was organized according to a structured relational model, as illustrated in Figure 63, and implemented within Power BI’s data modelling environment. **The developed model includes four main tables: “Sensor and Type,” “General Characteristics” “Entities and Exhibitions Table,” and “Available Variables”.** These are interconnected through relationships defined based on data logic and the need for filter propagation to support interactive visualisations. Since neither side of the relationship contains unique values, Power BI correctly identified the need for a many-to-many relationship. A controlled bidirectional filtering approach was chosen to enable cross-analysis between the technical characteristics of sensors and the variables they are capable of measuring. This approach was essential to ensure the analytical consistency of the model without compromising data integrity or the functionality of the interactive visualisations.

Figure 62: OIAR - Primary relational model.

Figure 63: OIAR - Microsoft Power BI structured relational mode used.

To ensure the integrity and reliability of the data used in the construction of the interactive dashboards, the Power Query Editor tool, integrated into Power BI, was used to carry out a systematic process of data transformation and cleaning. This step was essential for standardizing formats, correcting inconsistencies, and preparing the data for efficient exploratory analysis.

NAUTILOS OIAR Dashboards

A dashboard or Power BI panel is a page or screen within the software that enables highly interactive visualisation of data metrics in a single place (Shakiroh Khamis et al., 2024). **Dashboards have the ability to concisely summarize relevant information derived from large datasets, making it easier to quickly identify patterns and anomalies** (Sahaya et al., 2024). Among its benefits, customisation stands out - it allows users to tailor the visualisations to their own needs and the target audience, offering great flexibility. Users can explore the data visualisations interactively by selecting specific criteria, such as time periods, demographics, or outcomes, among others (Kenigsberg et al., 2022).

As part of the development of the first prototype of an interactive digital platform for OIAR in Power BI, **four main dashboards were designed**, each with specific objectives for data visualisation and exploration. The modular organisation allows users to access information in a segmented, intuitive manner, tailored to the type of analysis they wish to perform. All pages were developed with a focus on visual clarity, interactivity, and functional coherence.

Geographic Visualisation Dashboard

This dashboard is primarily designed to provide a geographic overview of the distribution of organisations involved in the production or commercialisation of ocean monitoring instrumentation (Figure 64). The central element is an interactive map, where countries with registered organisations are represented by circles whose size reflects the number of organisations located in each country.

Users can select a country directly on the map or apply filters by country name using the selection tools available in the interface. Among the data provided are the total number of registered organisations, the distribution of entities by category (such as industry, research, higher education institution, or others), the number of entities that commercialize sensors, and a list of the names of the organisations that do so.

The analysis of the geographic dashboard highlights a strong concentration of entities in the United Kingdom, followed by Canada. The analysis also made it possible to distinguish the profile of entities involved in ocean monitoring by country: in countries such as the United Kingdom and Canada, there is a strong industrial presence, while in Spain and Norway, most entities associated with ocean monitoring are research centers.

Figure 64: OIAR - Geographic Visualisation Dashboard.

Entity Search Dashboard

The second dashboard was developed to enable a detailed analysis of ocean monitoring instrumentation per organisation (Figure 65). Its structure is based on the application of combinable filters by country, organisation name, and instrument, allowing users to refine the results.

The dashboard's visual elements include the total count of instruments matching the selected criteria, and an interactive table displaying technical specifications such as instrument type, measurement range (minimum and maximum values), accuracy, resolution, and unit of measure. Additionally, a graph illustrates the operating depth of the selected instruments, allowing for a visual comparison and highlighting instrumentation capable of operating at depths of up to 11 000 meters.

This dashboard offers users a clear interface for comparing instruments and performing customized technical analysis, making it particularly useful in decision-making scenarios or market exploration. The dashboard also provides contextual information about the selected entity, including the organisation name and, when available, a link to the official sensor webpage.

Figure 65: OIAR - Entity Search Dashboard.

EOVs Analysis Dashboard

The third dashboard was developed to allow users to analyse the availability of sensors based on the variables they measure, using the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) categorisation (Figure 66). On this dashboard, users can select a variable of interest - such as pH - from a list of available options.

Selecting a variable immediately updates the dashboard's visualisations. A chart displays the number of sensors that measure the selected variable, making it easier to understand the availability of instruments for each environmental parameter. This visualisation helps identify

which variables have the greatest diversity of instrumentation and, conversely, where coverage gaps may exist.

The data reveals that the EOV types with the most available instruments are: Sea Surface Temperature, Subsurface Sea Temperature, and Surface Currents. On the other hand, variables such as pCO₂, Ocean Plastic Pollution, and Chlorophyll-*a* showed a lower diversity of instruments, which may indicate areas of limited technological development - either due to lower commercial demand or greater development challenges.

The dashboard also includes a table listing sensors corresponding to the selected variable, providing relevant information such as the responsible organisation, country of origin, instrument name, and, when available, a direct link to the instrument's official webpage.

Figure 66: OIAR - EOVs Analysis Dashboard.

Advanced Filtering Dashboard by Technical Specifications

This fourth dashboard was designed to enable advanced sensor searches based on specific operational and functional characteristics (Figure 67). Users can apply interactive filters to narrow down results using three main parameters: operating depth (entered as a numeric range), standalone operation, and the EOV measured. These criteria can be used in combination - for example, to select sensors capable of operating at depths of up to 600 meters, autonomously measuring dissolved oxygen.

This dashboard is particularly useful for users with specific technical requirements or those seeking to compare the operational capabilities of different sensors within a given performance range. Its flexibility supports the identification of equipment suited for complex monitoring projects, and it helped reveal trends such as the scarcity of high-depth autonomous sensors.

The search results are displayed in an interactive table that includes the instrument name, the responsible organisation, and a direct link to the sensor’s official webpage. This structure supports detailed technical analysis with immediate access to additional equipment information.

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Figure 67: OIAR - Advanced Filtering Dashboard by Technical Specifications.

Stakeholder Engagement and Validation Sessions

Two stakeholder interaction sessions were held with the participation of the University of Aveiro (UA) and CEiIA teams, and with involvement from the OIAR team to present the latest developments: the final database and the first Microsoft Power BI prototype of the Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap. All participants (around 50 people) explored the platform, tested its features, and shared improvement suggestions.

The first meeting took place on May 5, 2025, with members of CEiIA’s technical team (Figure 68). This session allowed for a first presentation of the tool and the collection of constructive feedback for its refinement - one of the main suggestions being the inclusion of a depth range selector for sensors, which was implemented in the “Advanced Filtering Dashboard by Technical Specification”.

Subsequently, on May 20, 2025, the final version OIAR was presented during the last NAUTILOS project meeting to the consortium. The solution was demonstrated live and tested in real time (Figure 68). The reception was very positive, with participants recognizing the tool’s usefulness, relevance, and potential - thus validating its value as a contribution to the project's objectives.

Figure 68: OIAR - Stakeholder engagement and validation sessions: in CEiiA (left) and during the last NAUTILOS CM in May 2025 (right).

OIAR - OUTCOMES AND STRATEGIC NEXT STEPS

Throughout the development of this work, it was possible to **collect, structure, and integrate a significant volume of data** related to the ocean monitoring market. This information was carefully **standardized, organized into relational tables, and integrated into an interactive solution**, leveraging the capabilities of Power BI. The dashboards created feature a clear and modular interface, with cross-filtering functionalities that adapt to different user profiles - from technical researchers to institutional managers or users with limited experience in data visualisation. The use of dynamic filters, segmentation by country, organisation, or variable, and the visual consistency across pages resulted in a fluid, intuitive solution that reinforced its alignment with the NAUTILOS project's strategic vision.

The **geographic distribution of the involved entities** became clearly visible, identifying the countries with the strongest presence in the ocean monitoring market and the key organisations involved - revealing development opportunities that could strengthen Europe's competitiveness. The OAIR also made it possible to identify **the most frequently monitored variables (EOVs) and, conversely, technological gaps, helping to guide innovation** investment within the ocean monitoring market - making this a **key tool for the allocation of European funding**. The advanced search functionality facilitates **access to a globally representative catalogue**, which could and should be continued.

As for future development of the OIAR, the main conclusions are summarized below - supporting what the OAIR team strongly believes is a strategic tool for the European Union in the context of its Blue Growth strategy. For the future, OIAR team suggests continuing this work with the following goals:

- **Online data collection:** Despite being very time-consuming, it proved to be the most effective method for gathering a broad and consistent dataset;
- **Stakeholder-driven data validation:** it is recommended to implement a validation mechanism allowing institutions to confirm their listed instrumentation;

Implementing an administration dashboard for partners to validate their own sensor data directly, could be an option to explore;

- **Direct stakeholder engagement:** Despite the need for budget allocation and logistical planning, in-person contact during trade fairs using a structured questionnaire was highly effective in both gathering data and promoting OAIR and should be considered in future OIAR developments;
- **Catalogue-style:** Avoid collecting or displaying sensitive information such as quotations. Keep the focus on commercial solutions (high TRL), maintain a catalogue-style format and refer users to the official supplier for further technical or commercial details;
- **AI tools:** Attempts to use AI tools for automatic data collection were not successful in this context. Nonetheless, the evolution of AI tools could allow for automated data compilation and updates in the future.

As a suggestion, **OAIR should be owned and maintained by a neutral institution**, at the European level, that can pursue **periodic database update, help ensure its long-term sustainability and prevent private or commercial misuse**. This would also support a long-term vision for OAIR by facilitating the integration of efforts with other databases developed under European projects - centralizing information, avoiding duplication of work, and enabling the platform to be made publicly accessible.

With this in mind, the success of this initiative also requires the creation of a **dedicated task force** that, in a structured manner and with the right expertise, can pursue efforts developed in the NAUTILOS project. Given the effort on data compilation and Power BI prototype design, **there's still a need to perform data validation, before making OIAR available online** (initial intention was to use NAUTILOS website - despite not being considered in NAUTILOS GA), thus leaving the opportunity for EU to decide the best way to share OIAR in the public domain, to achieve the operational OAIR that Europe truly needs.

XVI. SUMMARY

This report presents **11 sustainable business strategies** aiming to contribute to democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users. This work has been developed in the scope of WP11, a continuous and transversal WP focused on supporting NAUTILOS innovation process: from go-to-product to go-to-market.

By the end of the NAUTILOS project, **11 commercial products** are being made available, **all of them demonstrating significant and confirmed advantages for ocean monitoring** when compared to existing global market alternatives. A **comprehensive competitor and market analysis** revealed **75% of NAUTILOS key exploitable results** are the **most cost-effective in their class**, while the remaining **25% offer significant performance advantages**. The analysis (D11.5) included a benchmarking of **36 instruments** from competitors, primarily based in the **USA, Canada, Japan, and Europe** and was supported by the collection of **over 30 price quotations**. Notably, **two NAUTILOS KERs** were classified as "**new to market**" technologies, offering novel capabilities at advanced TRLs.

All of them are **commercial results with successful technical performance in a relevant environment (TRL6 or above)** following extensive scenario-based testing conducted across diverse platforms (e.g., autonomous vehicles, mooring buoys, research vessels, ships of opportunity) and deployed in multiple oceanic and maritime locations (see WP7 deliverables).

D11.7 intends to **detail each commercialisation strategy** and share **products business models**, covering all standard elements: customer segments, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships and cost structure. **11 BMCs were developed** for all KER partners, involving **2 external commercialisation partners**.

Most prominently, the technologies show strong applicability in **coastal survey and oceanographic research** and **oceanic observatories**, with consistent presence across multiple entries (Figure 69). Other sectors with broad coverage include fisheries, ports, and deep ocean research, indicating a wide scope of use. Overall, a global analysis suggested a **high degree of versatility and interdisciplinary potential** of the NAUTILOS KERs, particularly in areas related to **marine monitoring, research, and operational infrastructure**, as expected.

The socio-economic analysis (D11.5) highlights the far-reaching impact of NAUTILOS, with **total economic production projected to be comparable to the overall project budget**. Based on the final NAUTILOS KER selection, this estimate can now be confirmed as nearly equivalent. The social impact remains consistent, with an emphasis on **employing highly qualified personnel and promoting gender balance**.

As part of NAUTILOS' exploitation efforts, **11 NAUTILOS leaflets were produced, and 3 company-specific leaflets updated** featuring NAUTILOS products. Those materials as well as instruments developed were presented during **NAUTILOS brokerage events and other opportunities** (D11.3) at **7 international locations** (including USA, Italy, Spain, Denmark, France, Belgium, and the UK), resulting in **over 200 recorded interactions expressing commercial interest**, where all KERs were presented publicly to a wide audience of **early adopters, investors, and potential commercial partners**. Early sales were achieved with

WiSens - TD DO (NKE), while **joint projects** (e.g., with UL-FE with EMA Group) and **scalability initiatives** (e.g., involving the World Bank and BOOSTER) **to be continued beyond NAUTILOS** were launched to further expand development and market reach, since further efforts are necessary to conclude NAUTILOS KERs go-to market trajectory.

NAUTILOS KER	Sectors of the Blue Economy								
	Aquaculture	Coastal Tourism	Fisheries	Marine Biotechnology	Ocean Renewable Energies	Oceanic Observatories	Ports	Coastal Survey and Oceanographic Research	Deep Ocean Research
Fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor						x		x	x
Dissolved oxygen datalogger WiSens TD-DO	x		x			x		x	x
Fluorescence datalogger WiSens TD - Chl- <i>a</i>	x		x			x		x	
Silicate electrochemical sensor						x		x	x
Passive click and sound recorder	x		x		x	x		x	
Active acoustic profiling data logger AQUAscat Mk2	x				x	x		x	x
Submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics	x		x			x			x
Deep ocean CTD instrument / CT sensor	x	x	x			x	x	x	x
Deep ocean radioactivity sensor						x		x	x
MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tags						x		x	x
SRDL-CTD-Oxy animal tag						x			x

Figure 69: Cross-sector relevance of NAUTILOS key exploitable results, highlighting their connection to various Blue Economy sectors.

In addition, the project also contributed to the democratisation of access to information, making previously scattered or hard-to-access data, available through a clear, accessible, and customizable platform - OIAR. **OIAR centralizes information on existing instruments: 313 entities, from over 30 countries; 390 instruments; 4 dashboards.** D11.7 also reports on the development of **the first Microsoft Power BI prototype of the Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap.** Suggestions for the future development of the OIAR were presented, aiming to foster the future for this strategic tool for the European Union in the context of its Blue Growth strategy. This WP11 activity stood out not only for the complexity involved, but also for the strategic importance of its application. Ocean monitoring is a global priority, and tools like this can help accelerate innovation, improve research efficiency, and promote a more informed and sustainable use of technological resources. In doing so, they support the development of the Blue Economy and strengthen Europe's competitiveness in marine and maritime domains.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	NAUTILOS Instrumentation results	https://nautilus-h2020.eu/sensors-samplers/
2	NAUTILOS data and modelling products results - ERDDAP	https://data-nautilus-h2020.eu/erddap/index.html
3	NAUTILOS data and modelling products results – Data Portal	https://nautilus-h2020.eu/data-portal/
4	NAUTILOS data and modelling products results – Model Portal	https://nautilus-h2020.eu/model-portal/
5	Policy briefs results	https://nautilus-h2020.eu/policy-engagement/
6	Citizen science tools results	https://nautilus-h2020.eu/nautilus-cs-app/
7	NAUTILOS Grant Agreement	NAUTILOS Team Drive
8	NAUTILOS Consortium Agreement	NAUTILOS Team Drive
9	NAUTILOS D7.1 - Fisheries and Aquaculture Observing Systems demonstration mid-term	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14260995
10	NAUTILOS D7.2 - Fisheries and Aquaculture Observing Systems demonstration final report	NAUTILOS Team Drive
11	NAUTILOS D7.4 - Augmented Observing Systems demonstrations final report	NAUTILOS Team Drive
12	NAUTILOS D7.5 - Report on the demonstration of silicate sensor on ARGO float in the Mediterranean Sea	NAUTILOS Team Drive
13	NAUTILOS D7.6 - Report on Animal Borne Instruments demonstrations	NAUTILOS Team Drive
14	NAUTILOS D9.7 - KPI assessment 2	NAUTILOS Team Drive
15	NAUTILOS D10.3 – Policy Briefs and dissemination results	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10702521
16	NAUTILOS D10.9 - Report on Citizen Science Campaigns (WP10)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14856149
17	NAUTILOS D10.10 – Dissemination Impact Report – 2	NAUTILOS Team Drive
18	NAUTILOS D11.1 - NAUTILOS Exploitation Strategy	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7211802
19	NAUTILOS D11.2 - Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap (development)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887016

20	NAUTILOS D11.3 - Brokerage Events Meetings Protocols	NAUTILOS Team Drive
21	NAUTILOS D11.5 - NAUTILOS Socio-Economic Impact Assessment – final	NAUTILOS Team Drive
22	NAUTILOS D11.8 - NAUTILOS Socio-Economic Impact Assessment	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887043
23	NAUTILOS D12.2 - Publication of ESPCE - related citizen science data and graphical maps in the citizen science interface	NAUTILOS Team Drive
24	NAUTILOS D12.3 - Report on Citizen Science Campaigns (WP12)	NAUTILOS Team Drive
25	Al-Sulaiti, A., Mansour, M., Al-Yafei, H., Aseel, S., Kucukvar, M., & Onat, N. C. (2021). Using Data Analytics and Visualization Dashboard for Engineering, Procurement, and Construction Project's Performance Assessment. 2021 IEEE 8th International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Applications (ICIEA), 207–211.	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIEA52957.2021.9436728
26	Kenigsberg, T. A., Hause, A. M., McNeil, M. M., Nelson, J. C., Ann Shoup, J., Goddard, K., Lou, Y., Hanson, K. E., Glenn, S. C., & Weintraub, E. S. (2022). Dashboard development for near real-time visualization of COVID-19 vaccine safety surveillance data in the Vaccine Safety Datalink. <i>Vaccine</i> , 40(22), 3064–3071.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2022.04.010
27	Možek, M., Pečar, B., & Vrtačnik, D. (2024). Cost-Efficient Oceanographic Instrument with Microfabricated Sensors for Measuring Conductivity, Temperature and Depth of Seawater. <i>Sensors</i> , 24(12), 3940.	https://doi.org/10.3390/s24123940
28	Pinho, B., Coelho, M. I., Faria, R., Fernandes, S. (2025). Desenvolvimento de um Power BI para análise de dados sobre instrumentação de monitorização oceânica no contexto do projeto NAUTILOS. Projeto em Engenharia e Gestão Industrial Projeto em Engenharia e Gestão Industrial. Universidade de Aveiro.	<i>n.a.</i>
29	Sahaya, A. P. N., Purnawarman, D., Rasyidah, F. S., Prabowo, Y. D., Sarwo, & Gatc, J. (2024). Powering Sales Insights: A Comparative Analysis of Data Visualization Tools, Microsoft Power BI vs Tableau. 2024 9th International Conference on Business and Industrial Research (ICBIR), 1042–1047.	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICBIR61386.2024.10875740
30	Shakiroh Khamis, Mazida Ahmad, Azizah Ahmad, Hapini Awang, Chrissanthi Angeli, Zanariah Zainudin, Lim Jit Theam, Wong Pei Voon, & Nurul Syafidah	https://doi.org/10.37934/araset.48.1.283298

	Jamil. (2024). Knowledge Visualization of Internet Usage Pattern to Improve Students' Academic Performance Using Prescriptive Analytic. Journal of Advanced Research in Applied Sciences and Engineering Technology, 48(1), 283–298.	
31	BIMS Institute	https://www.blackinmarinescience.org/bims-institute.html
32	Booster Initiative	www.horizonresultsbooster.eu
33	British Antarctic Survey	https://www.bas.ac.uk/
34	Charles Darwin Foundation	https://www.darwinfoundation.org/en/
35	CNR	https://www.cnr.it/en
36	DTU AQUA	https://www.aqua.dtu.dk/english/
37	East China Normal University	https://english.ecnu.edu.cn/
38	EIC Accelerator	https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-accelerator_en
39	EMA Group	https://group.ema.si/
40	Fugro	https://www.fugro.com/
41	FVON - Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network	https://fvon.org/
41	Galapagos National Park	https://galapagos.gob.ec/?lang=en
43	HORST	https://horst.gr/about-us-gr/
44	INILAB	https://inilab.dk/
45	Jocotoco Foundation	https://jocotoco.org/web2#/EN/home2
46	KIMO International	https://www.kimointernational.org/
47	Kolmården Zoo	https://www.kolmarden.com/en
48	LandSeaLot project	https://landsealot.eu/
49	Manta Trust	https://www.mantatrust.org/
50	MOWI UK	https://mowi.com/uk/
51	National Oceanography Centre UK	https://noc.ac.uk/
52	National Research Council Canada	https://nrc.canada.ca/en
53	PNO Innovation	https://www.pnoconsultants.com/pt/
54	Portofino Marine Mammal Sanctuary	https://portofinodivers.com/diving/portofino/marine-park
55	RBINS	https://www.naturalsciences.be/en
56	RPS Group	https://www.rpsgroup.com/
57	RWE	https://www.rwe.com/en/
58	Save Our Seas Foundation	https://saveourseas.com/

59	Seaglow	https://seaglow.eu/
60	SLU	https://www.slu.se/en/
61	SMRU UK	https://www.smru.st-andrews.ac.uk/
62	Sternula	https://www.sternula.com/
63	Strategyzer	www.strategyzer.com
64	Universidad San Francisco de Quito	https://www.usfq.edu.ec/es
65	Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale	https://www.univ-littoral.fr/
66	Université Laval	https://www.ulaval.ca/
67	University of Vigo	https://www.uvigo.gal/en
68	US Geological Survey	https://www.usgs.gov/
69	World Bank Group	www.worldbank.org

APPENDIX 2: NAUTILOS KER DESIGNATIONS

NAUTILOS KERs evolved from the initial expected project results (describe in NAUTILOS grant agreement) into commercial products. Throughout the project, modifications were made namely considering their final designation. The evolution of NAUTILOS KERs designations is summarized in Table A2 - 1 (based on a previous version presented in D11.5, with a few additional updates).

Table A2 - 1: Evolution of NAUTILOS KERs designations: from grant agreement designation to commercial product designation (based on a previous version presented in D11.5, with a few additional updates in bold).

GRANT AGREEMENT DESIGNATION	COMMERCIAL PRODUCT DESIGNATION
Fluorometric Sensors/dissolved oxygen	Fluorometric dissolved oxygen sensor
Dissolved Oxygen and Fluorescence Sensors	Dissolved oxygen data logger WiSens TD-DO
	Fluorescence data logger WiSens TD – Chl- α
Silicate Electrochemical Sensor	Silicate electrochemical sensor
Passive broadband acoustic recording sensor for noise monitoring	Click and sound recorder
Passive acoustic event recorder (porpoise & dolphin clicks for abundance estimation)	
Active Acoustic Profiling Sensor	Active acoustic profiling data logger AQUAscat Mk2
Sampler for Nanoplastics and Microplastics	Submersible sampler for nanoplastics and microplastics
Deep ocean CTD	Deep ocean CTD instrument / CT sensor
Deep ocean low-level radioactivity sensor	Deep ocean low-level radioactivity sensor
Animal-borne instruments	MAANTA NAUTILOS animal tag
	SRDL-CTD-OXY animal tag

APPENDIX 3: OIAR INSTRUMENTATION CATALOGUE

The instrumentation considered for the Open Access Instrumentation Roadmap is listed in Table A3 - 1. Information was primarily collected from the official websites of the institutions developing the instruments. NAUTILOS partners (AQUATEC, NKE, and SubCTech) validated the data related to their respective entries.

Table A3 - 1: List of instrumentation for ocean monitoring, compiled for the OIAR database, including a reference to the developer organisation (name and website).

INSTITUTION NAME	INSTITUTION WEBSITE	INSTRUMENT
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	HydroC CO ₂
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	CONTROS HydroC [®] CH ₄ FT
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	CONTROS HydroC [®] CH ₄
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	CONTROS HydroC [®] CO ₂ FT
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	CONTROS HydroFIA [®] pH
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	CONTROS HydroFIA [®] TA
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	FerryBox
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	PocketFerryBox
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	Self cleaning monitoring box (SMB)
-4H-Jena engineering GmbH	https://www.4h-jena.de/en/start/	Active/Passive Sampler
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	https://www.aanderaa.com/	4420/4420R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	https://www.aanderaa.com/	4520/4520R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	https://www.aanderaa.com/	4930/4930R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	https://www.aanderaa.com/	4117/4117R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	https://www.aanderaa.com/	4835
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	https://www.aanderaa.com/	4296
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5819/5819R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5990
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	4830/4830R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5400/5400R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5402/5402R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5403/5403R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5800 / 5810 / 5800R / 5800RR / 5810E
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5730
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	4330W/4330/4330F
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	4531
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	4831W/4831/4831F
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	SeaGuardII DCP Wave
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	4060/4060R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	SEAGUARD [®] WLR Water Level Recorder
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5217/5217R
Aanderaa Data Instruments AS.	http://www.aanderaa.com/	5218/5218R

Abyssens	https://www.abysse.fr/	DORI Underwater Acoustic Recorder (XS Model)
Abyssens	http://www.abysse.fr/	MOBI Real-Time Acoustic Monitoring Buoy
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	P65 Smart™ Transom Mount
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	B122 Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	B17-HP Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	DST810 Smart™ Multisensor with Gen2 Paddlewheel
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	DT800 Smart™ Sensor SST Thru-hull NMEA 0183
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	DT800 Smart™ Sensor SST Thru-hull NMEA 2000®
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	HT200 Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	P39 Smart™ TRIDUCER® Multisensor/CW Transom Mount
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	P79S Smart™ Sensor In-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST800 Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST850 Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	UDST800 Ultrasonic Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull NMEA 2000®
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	UST800 Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull NMEA 2000®
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	UST850 Smart™ Sensor Thru-hull NMEA 2000®
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST61 Transom Mount
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST63 Transom Mount
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST800 Speed and Temperature Analog Output
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST850 Speed and Temperature Analog Output
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST900 Speed and Temperature Sensor Plastic
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST950 Speed and Temperature Sensor Plastic
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	T42 Temperature Sensor Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	DX900+ Multilog Electromagnetic Speed/Temp Sensor, Plastic Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST300 Shorty™ Thru-hull
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST69 Transom Mount
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST800 Speed and Temperature Sensor Plastic Thru-hull Analog
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	ST850 Speed and Temperature Sensor Bronze Thru-hull Analog
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	T80 Temperature Sensor
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	G2183 GPS
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	GH2183 Heading & GPS
Airmar Technology	http://www.airmar.com/	H2183 Heading Sensor
Alpha Controls	https://www.alphacontrols.com/	GF Signet Gen II
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3

AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-6
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Sound Velocity Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Sound Velocity & Temperature Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Conductivity & Temperature Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Pressure Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Temperature Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Dissolved Oxygen Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Turbidity Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Turbidity with Wiper Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR CDOM Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Chlorophyll A&B Red Excitation Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Chlorophyll A&B Blue Excitation Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Crude Oils Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Fluorescein Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Optical Brighteners Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Phycocyanin Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Phycoerythrin (BGA) Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Refined Fuels Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Rhodamine Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com	AML-3 / AML-6 LGR Tryptophan Sensor
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com/	X2change™ High Accuracy Conductivity-Temperature
AML Oceanographic	https://amloceanographic.com/	X2change™ High Accuracy Pressure
AMT GmbH	https://www.amt-gmbh.com/index.html	AMT GmbH Dissolved Oxygen Sensor
AMT GmbH	https://www.amt-gmbh.com/index.html	AMT GmbH CO2 sensor
AMT GmbH	https://www.amt-gmbh.com/index.html	AMT GmbH pH sensor
AMT GmbH	https://www.amt-gmbh.com/index.html	AMT GmbH Redox sensor
AMT GmbH	https://www.amt-gmbh.com/index.html	AMT GmbH 7-pole Conductivity Sensor
AMT GmbH	https://www.amt-gmbh.com/index.html	AMT GmbH Temperature sensor
ANB Sensors	https://www.anbsensors.com/	OC300
ANB Sensors	https://www.anbsensors.com/	OC1250
ANB Sensors	http://www.anbsensors.com/	AQ5

ANB Sensors	http://www.anbsensors.com/	AQ50
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Combined PH - ORP sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Dissolved Oxygen (DO) sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Electrical Conductivity (EC) sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Water Temperature Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Salinity Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Total Dissolved Solids Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Sea water specific gravity (SSG) Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread RES Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Depth Sensor (Aquaprobe / Aquasonde)
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Ammonium /Ammonia Water Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Chloride Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Fluoride sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Nitrate Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Calcium Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Turbidity Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Chlorophyll Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Blue-Green Algae sensors
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Rhodamine Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Fluorescein Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread Refined Oil Sensor
Aquaread	https://www.aquaread.com/	Aquaread CDOM sensor
AQUATEC	https://www.aquatecgroup.com	AQUAlogger® 310TY
AQUATEC	https://www.aquatecgroup.com	AQUAlogger 520
AQUATEC	https://www.aquatecgroup.com	AQUAlogger 530WTD
AQUATEC	https://www.aquatecgroup.com	AQUAlogger® 310PT
AQUATEC	https://www.aquatecgroup.com	HYDROlog™ 3000PT
AQUATEC	https://www.aquatecgroup.com	AQUAcat® 1000R
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROlog 3400
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROlog 9-Series
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUAcat® 1000R Deep
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROgauge®Mk 2
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	LEAKlog® LR Fluorometer
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	LEAKlog® PA1 Passive Acoustic Leak Detector
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	LEAKlog® T1 Temperature Probe
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUAcat® 1000L
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUAlogger® 110 - Leak Detection Data Acquisition Unit
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUAcat® 1000S
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUAcat® 1000LT

AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	KINEKtron®
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROskid™ 3000 - Monitoring Skid
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROlog™ 3100 - Hydrotest - Deck
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROlog™ 3000F - Flow Logger
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUALogger® 530WTD
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUALogger® 520 - Mini Pressure Logger
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUALogger® 110 - Leak Detection Data Acquisition Unit
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUAscat® 1000S
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	AQUAscat® 1000LT
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	KINEKtron®
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROskid™ 3000 - Monitoring Skid
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROlog™ 3100 - Hydrotest - Deck
AQUATEC	http://www.aquatecgroup.com/	HYDROlog™ 3000F - Flow Logger
ASL Environmental Sciences	https://www.aslenv.com/index.html	AZFP
ASL Environmental Sciences	https://www.aslenv.com/index.html	AZFP-nano
ASL Environmental Sciences	https://www.aslenv.com/index.html	IPS
ASL Environmental Sciences	https://www.aslenv.com/index.html	Wave Profiler
Atomtex	https://atomtex.com/en	AT6104DM Spectrometer
BioSonics	https://www.biosonicsinc.com/	MX Aquatic Habitat Echo Sounder
Blue Atlas Robotics	https://blueatlasrobotics.com/	Sentinus
BRÜEL & KJÆR	https://www.bksv.com	TYPE 8105
BRÜEL & KJÆR	https://www.bksv.com	Type 8106
Bruker	https://www.bruker.com/en.html	INVENIO
Centro Tecnológico Naval y del Mar	https://ctnaval.com/	Load sensor deployed in a aquaculture farm
Centro Tecnológico Naval y del Mar	https://ctnaval.com/	Metocean buoy
Centro Tecnológico Naval y del Mar	https://ctnaval.com/	Net sensor
Chelonia	https://www.chelonia.co.uk/	Deep F-POD
Chelsea Tehcnologies	https://chelsea.co.uk/	Trilux
Chelsea Tehcnologies	https://chelsea.co.uk/	Uvilux
ClearWater Sensors	https://www.clearwatersensors.com/index.html	Lab-on-chip Chemical Silicate Sensor
D-2 Incorporated	https://www.d-2.com	D-2 Inc. Hybrid CTD
D-2 Incorporated	https://www.d-2.com	Ocean CT Sensor
D-2 Incorporated	https://www.d-2.com	Hybrid CTD
Dartmouth Ocean Technologies	https://dartmouthocean.com/	A1000-200
Dartmouth Ocean Technologies	https://dartmouthocean.com/	Alkalinity Sensor
Dartmouth Ocean Technologies	https://dartmouthocean.com/	eDNA Sampler
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	EIVA Pressure sensor
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	Nano transponder with depth sensor

EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	ToughBoy Panchax 1.9 with 300 kHz ADCP
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	ToughBoy Panchax 1.9 with 600 kHz ADCP
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	ToughBoy Panchax 1.9 with 1200 kHz ADCP
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	ToughBoy Panchax 1.9 without fitted ADCP
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	Octans Subsea
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	SPRINT-Nav 505 4k System
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	SPRINT 505 4k System
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	Syrinx DVL 4k
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	Side Scan Sonar 4205
EIVA	https://www.eiva.com/	NORBIT iWBMSH
ElectricBlue	https://electricblue.eu/	EnvLogger
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Oxymax COS41
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Oxymax COS61
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Oxymax COS61D
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Orbisint CPS11
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Memosens CCS55E
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Memosens COS51E
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Proline Promag H 200
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Cubemass DCI
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Proline Prowirl F 200
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Proline Promag H 100
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Proline Promass E 200
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Proline Prowirl R 200
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Proline Promass E 100
Endress+Hauser	https://www.endress.com/	Proline Promag E100
Falmouth Scientific Inc.	https://www.falmouth.com/	ACM-PLUS
Falmouth Scientific Inc.	https://www.falmouth.com/	ACM-WAVE-PLUS
Falmouth Scientific Inc.	https://www.falmouth.com/	ACM-PLUS-MP
Falmouth Scientific Inc.	https://www.falmouth.com/	WAVE-TIDE-PLUS
Falmouth Scientific Inc.	https://www.falmouth.com/	Tide Monitoring System
Fluidion	https://fluidion.com/	Deep Water Sampler
Flydog	https://www.flydogmarine.com/	Microplastic Sampler
GeoAcoustics	https://www.geoacoustics.com/	GeoPulse Compact OTS
GeoAcoustics	https://www.geoacoustics.com/	GeoPulse 2
GeoAcoustics	https://www.geoacoustics.com/	Pulsar
GeoAcoustics	https://www.geoacoustics.com/	GeoScan 2361
Horiba	https://www.horiba.com/int/	MacroRAM
Hydroptic	http://www.hydroptic.com/index.php/public/Pa ge/products_list/	UVP6-LP
Hydroptic	http://www.hydroptic.com/index.php/public/Pa ge/products_list/	UVP6-HF
Hydroptic	http://www.hydroptic.com/index.php/public/Pa ge/products_list/	ZooSCAN
Hydroptic	http://www.hydroptic.com/index.php/public/Pa ge/products_list/	UVP5

Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it/	Ocean Seven 308
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it/	Ocean Seven 306
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it	OCEAN SEVEN 320 PLUS
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it	Idronaut Pressure Sensor
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it	Idronaut Temperature Sensor
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it	Idronaut Conductivity Sensor
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it	Idronaut Conductivity, Temperature and Oxygen Sensor
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it	Idronaut pH Sensor
Idronaut	https://www.idronaut.it	KCl Reference Sensor
Impact Subsea	https://www.impactsubsea.co.uk/	ISD4000
In-Situ	https://in-situ.com/uk/	Aqua TROLL 800
KC Denmark	https://www.kc-denmark.dk	Plastic particle pump
Keller	https://keller-druck.com/en/	Seires 4LD
Little Leonardo	https://l-leo.com/eng/	ORI400-3MPD3GT
MarSensing	https://www.marsensing.com/pt/	digitalHyd SR-1
McLane Research Laboratories, Inc.	https://mclanelabs.com	Particle and Phytoplankton Sampler (PPS)
MetOcean Telematics	https://metocean.com/	Stokes Drifter
MetOcean Telematics	https://www.metocean.com	CODE/DAVIS Drifter
MetOcean Telematics	https://www.metocean.com	iSPHERE
MetOcean Telematics	https://www.metocean.com	iSVP
MetOcean Telematics	https://www.metocean.com	iSVP-RXL
Miros AS	http://www.miros-group.com/	Wavex
Miros AS	https://www.miros-group.com	RangeFinder
MiWire Group	https://miwire.net/	SeaWire
National Oceanography Centre	https://noc-innovations.com/	Robotic Cartridge Sampling Instrument (RoCSI)
National Oceanography Centre	https://noc.ac.uk/	Alkalinity Sensor
National Oceanography Centre	https://noc.ac.uk/	Lab on chip sensor
National Oceanography Centre	https://noc.ac.uk/	Optode sensors
National Oceanography Centre	https://noc.ac.uk/	Silicate sensor
NKE	https://nke-instrumentation.com/	Silicate sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiMo
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Phyco-C Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Phyco-E Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation CDOM Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Chloride Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	Wimo Plus
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Ammonium Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation CT Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation TBD Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation DO Sensor

nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Chlorophyll A Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation pH Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Redox / ORP Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Crude Oil Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	nke Instrumentation Nitrate Sensor
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens TD
nke Instrumentation	https://nautilus-h2020.eu/	WiSens TD - DO
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens T6000
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens CTD
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens CTDS
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens CTDSV
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens TBD
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens Wave
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens DO
nke Instrumentation	https://nke-instrumentation.com	WiSens Chloro a
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	DVL500
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	AWAC - 1 MHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	AWAC - 600 kHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	AWAC - 400 kHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Signature1000
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Signature500
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Signature250
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Signature100
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Signature55
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp 500 m
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp 6000 m
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp Profiler 2 MHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp Profiler 1 MHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp Profiler 600 kHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp Profiler 400 kHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp Z-Cell 1 MHz
Nortek	https://www.nortekgroup.com	Aquadopp Z-Cell 400 kHz
Ocean Diagnostics	https://oceandiagnostics.com	Ascension Microplastic Depth Sampler
Ocean Instruments	https://www.oceaninstruments.co.nz/	SoundTrap ST600 STD
Ocean Sonics	https://oceansonics.com/	icListen HF ALTA
Ocean Sonics	https://oceansonics.com/	icListen Smart Hydrophone
Ocean Sonics	https://oceansonics.com/	icListen Rb9-ETH
Ocean Sonics	https://oceansonics.com/	Digital hydrophone array
OSIL	https://osil.com/	Microplastic sampler
Planet Ocean	https://planet-ocean.co.uk/	NEP-5000
Pro-Oceanus	https://pro-oceanus.com/	CO2-Pro CV
Pro-Oceanus	https://pro-oceanus.com/	Pro-Oceanus GTD-Pro
Pro-Oceanus	https://pro-oceanus.com/	Mini CO2

Pro-Oceanus	https://pro-oceanus.com/	Mini TDGP
Pro-Oceanus	https://pro-oceanus.com/	Mini CH4
Proteus Instruments	https://proteus-instruments.com/	Proteus Multiparameter Water Quality Meter
Pyroscience	https://www.pyroscience.com/en/	AquapHOx-LX
Pyroscience	https://www.pyroscience.com/en/	AquapHOx-TX
Qingdao Daowan Technology Co., Ltd.	http://www.daowantech.cn/en/index.php	DW16
RBR	https://rbr-global.com/	RBRcoda ³
RBR	https://rbr-global.com/	RBRduet ³
RBR	https://rbr-global.com/	RBRbrevio ³
RBR	https://rbr-global.com/	RBRtridente
Rockland Scientific	https://rocklandscientific.com/	MicroRider
RS Aqua	https://rsaqua.co.uk/	Orca
RS Aqua	https://rsaqua.co.uk/	Porpoise 84D
s::can	https://www.s-can.at/en/	spectro::lyser titanium pro
s::can	https://www.s-can.at/en/	condu::lyser
s::can	https://www.s-can.at/en/	redo::lyser
s::can	https://www.s-can.at/en/	pH::lyser
s::can	https://www.s-can.at/en/	oxi::lyser
SatLab	https://www.satlab.com.se/	Hydroflow
SAVI A/S	https://saiv.no/	SD208
Scienta Envinet	https://scientaenvinet.com/en/	TUNA
Sea & Sun Technology	https://www.sea-sun-tech.com/	CTD48
Sea & Sun Technology	https://www.sea-sun-tech.com/	CTD60Mc
Sea & Sun Technology	https://www.sea-sun-tech.com/	LED-Fluorometer
Sea and Sun Technology GmbH	https://www.sea-sun-tech.com	CTD48
Sea-Bird Scientific	https://www.seabird.com/	SBE 49 FastCAT CTD
Sea-Bird Scientific	https://www.seabird.com/	Glider Payload CTD
Sea-Bird Scientific	https://www.seabird.com/	Deep SUNA Nitrate Sensor
Sea-Bird Scientific	https://www.seabird.com/	ECO Triplet
Sea-Bird Scientific	https://www.seabird.com/	SBE 37-SIP MicroCAT
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	FGM3D UW Series
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	FGM3D / 125-C3T
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	FGM3D
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	FGM3D UWD
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	FGM650
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	FGM400
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	FGM3D TD
SENSYS Sensorik and Systemtechnologie GmbH	http://www.sensysmagnetometers.com/	LSUW
Sequoia Scientific, Inc.	http://www.sequoiasci.com/	LISST-ABS

Sequoia Scientific, Inc.	http://www.sequoiasci.com/	LISST-AOBS
Solinst	https://www.solinst.com/	Solinst Levellogger 5 LTC
Sonardyne	https://www.sonardyne.com/	Origin 600
Sonardyne	https://www.sonardyne.com/	Syrinx
Sonardyne	https://www.sonardyne.com/	Type 8195
Ss. CYRIL AND METHODIUS UNIVERSITY IN SKOPJE (FTM-UCIM)	https://archive.ukim.edu.mk/en_index.php	SPE based on PANI/CNT and PANI/G electropolymerized NC for pH of ocean waters
Sternula	https://www.sternula.com/	MMS proxy
SubCtech GmbH	https://subctech.com/	OceanXpert-Sea IR-CO2
SubCtech GmbH	https://subctech.com/	OceanPack RACE
SubCtech GmbH	https://subctech.com/	Microplastic Sampler
SubCtech GmbH	https://subctech.com/	SuNaMips
SubCtech GmbH	https://subctech.com/	OceanXpert-Lab IR-CO2
SubCtech GmbH	https://subctech.com/	OceanPack RACK
SubCtech GmbH	https://subctech.com/	Plankton/Microplastic Sampler
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	DEFI2-CT
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	DEFI2-T
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	DEFI2-D
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	DEFI2-DHG
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	DEFI2-L
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	Mini-Pro CH4
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	Mini-Pro CO2
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	CO2-Pro
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	CO2-Pro-CV
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	Swale Technologies GTD-Pro
Swale Technologies	http://swaleocean.co.uk/	Swale Technologies pH sensor
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-pH200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-ORP200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-EC200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-TDS200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-DO200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-TUR200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-SS200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-MLSS200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-CHL200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	SH-BGA200
Systea	https://www.systea.it/en/	WIZ probe
Teledyne RD Instruments	https://www.teledynemarine.com/brands/rdi	Workhorse II Sentinel ADCP
Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	SWIFT CTD
Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	SWIFT Deep CTD
Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	SWIFT SVP
Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	Model 803
Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	ultraSV OEM
Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	OEM
Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	miniSVS

Teledyne Valeport	https://www.valeport.co.uk/	Midas CTD
Turner Designs	https://www.turnerdesigns.com/	C3
Turner Designs	https://www.turnerdesigns.com/	C-sense
Turner Designs	https://www.turnerdesigns.com/	Turbidity Plus
Turner Designs	http://www.turnerdesigns.com/	Trilogy Laboratory Fluorometer
Water Linked	https://waterlinked.com	DVL A50
Water Linked	https://waterlinked.com	DVL A125
YSI	https://www.y.si.com/sontek	SonTek M9
YSI	https://www.y.si.com/	EXO2